

D2.1- Multidisciplinary cross-organizational research teams

Project acronym:	CiRCLETECH
Project full title:	CiRCLETECH – Twinning partnership to deliver enhanced networking for circular technological and socioeconomic impact, raising research excellence and strengthening management capacity
Grant agreement no.:	101079354
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Reviewed:	Aranka Földessy
Approved:	Aranka Földessy
Document Reference:	CiRCLETECH – D2.1
Dissemination Level:	PU
Version:	1.0
Date:	31.01.2023

Funded by the
European Union

This project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101079354.

History of Changes

Version	Date	Modification reason	Modified by
0.1	06.11.2022	Initial structure	Imre Gombkötő
0.2	12.12.2022	Initial content added	Imre Gombkötő
0.3	17.01.2023	Initial content added	Nina Boorsma
0.4	21.01.2023	Review and revise content, add annexes, formatting to a template format	Imre Gombkötő
0.5	25.01.2023	Initial content added; Review and revise content	David Peck, Nina Boorsma
0.8	28.01.2023	Quality check	Imre Gombkötő
1.0	30.01.2023	Final reviewed deliverable	Nina Boorsma / Imre Gombkötő

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List of abbreviations

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
EU	European Union
HE	Horizon Europe
IDP	Individual Development Plan
LUT	Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology LUT
RGP	Research Group Plan
TUD	TU Delft
UNIM	University of Miskolc
DCI	Delft Circularity Initiative
CBE	Circular Built Environment hub
FIEK	Establishment of Advanced Materials and Smart Technologies
GVA	Gross Value Added
REE	Rare Earth Elements
WEEE	Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment
EEE	Electrical and Electronic equipment
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
EoU	End-of-Use
EoL	End-of-Life
CM	Circular Manufacturing
ErP	Energy-related Products
GHGs	GreenHouse Gas emissions
TOE	Ton of Oil
CEE	Central and Eastern Europe
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
LCOE	Levelized Lost Of Energy
IDP	Individual Development Plan
RGP	Research Group Plan
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators

1. Executive Summary

The **CIRCLETECH** project's primary objective is to raise the scientific excellence of the University of Miskolc (UNIM) in the field of sustainable circular economy research, intending to form a long-lasting Research Hub across Northern Hungary.

UNIM has recognized gaps and the institution also sees regional opportunities, also on a wider scale, in intensifying its research activity in the field of Sustainable Circular Economy, by offering to address these objectives, four **cross-organizational multidisciplinary** research teams are created, where research is led by established researchers from UNIM, supervised by lead researchers from TU DELFT or LUT UNIVERSITY. Teams mutually work together on the different subtopics, applying dynamic research methodology while continuously exchanging views and results to create synergies between efforts. These topics are:

- Research subtopic #1: Urban and waste mining, material recycling
- Research subtopic #2: Processing technologies in waste recycling
- Research subtopic #3: Circular manufacturing
- Research subtopic #4: Sustainable energy transition – Just transition

Identifying the technology gap allows the research teams to investigate sustainable, circular approaches via the lens of societal, company, economic, and policy perspectives. This will help inform on barriers to establishing a successful hub in the target region.

The report analyzes selected existing research hubs across all three **CIRCLETECH** partners. The descriptions of these hubs from the three universities indicate what objectives existing hubs have and what elements the hubs are made up of.

This report outlines the description of the four research subtopics by UMIN, LUT and TUD, identifying how those are connected to major European Strategies, and actions, allowing for the mapping, identification, and connection to the topics to the European Research and Innovation calls foreseen in 2023 and 2024 (HEU working programs for 2023-24).

Teams will work in interaction with each other compiling a set of measures and solutions, as described in the report for real take-up of technological innovations and their integration into the circular economy, with a particular interest in the materials flow of industrial cycles. An important measure is the KPIs, around education, research, mobility, and grants. Their performance and any new risks should be regularly reviewed and updated.

It is clear that the existing circular, sustainable actions taken by the partners in the **CIRCLETECH** project are robust and deliver meaningful impact. They provide a good base of knowledge and experience to build the four themes going forwards. By engaging with colleagues carefully, the impact and success of the four themes are heightened. The early stages of the **CIRCLETECH** project have ensured that the 'teams' aspect of the multidisciplinary, cross-organizational teams is robustly established.

2. Introduction

The **CiRCLETECH** project's primary objective is to raise the scientific excellence of the University of Miskolc (UNIM) in the field of sustainable circular economy research, intending to form a long-lasting Research Hub across Northern Hungary. The creation of the operating framework of joint research will help set up the basis of long-lasting research cooperation in the field of Sustainable Circular Economy, enabling the elaboration of joint research ideas and helping the uptake of technological research results in the area. The creation of the **CiRCLETECH** Hub, through the activities of the **CiRCLETECH** project, provides the basis for future cooperation and operation of a regional excellence centre creating a meaningful impact on the regional and national level on the circular economy, but also on involvement in Horizon Europe (H-E).

This report shows how we will define and develop a successful sustainable circular research hub, building from selected, existing, research hubs at all 3 partners, which were analysed to learn from and to provide inspiration. The report explains the aim and scope of their unique strengths, as well as the audience they address.

The UNIM has a special interest in Materials Sciences and is focusing on excellence in research for a more sustainable, circular economy. The Internal Development Strategy of the institution explicitly sets the goal of increasing the visibility of the university internationally. Participating in international research activity and especially projects funded by the R&D framework programs of the European Union (EU), are the ideal vehicle for achieving this goal. UNIM is, however, still lagging in maximizing investment in R&D and turning that into stronger, sustainable, regional economic growth.

UNIM has recognized this gap and the institution also sees regional opportunities, also on a wider scale, in intensifying its research activity in the field of Sustainable Circular Economy, by offering to address these objectives, four **cross-organizational multidisciplinary** research teams are created, where research is led by established researchers from UNIM, supervised by lead researchers from TU DELFT or LUT UNIVERSITY. Teams mutually work together on the different subtopics, applying dynamic research methodology while continuously exchanging views and results to create synergies between efforts. These topics are the following:

- Research subtopic #1: Urban and waste mining, material recycling
- Research subtopic #2: Processing technologies in waste recycling
- Research subtopic #3: Circular manufacturing
- Research subtopic #4: Sustainable energy transition – Just transition

The research on the above-mentioned topics will be carried out based on the identification of the level of sustainable technologies currently used by the companies operating in Northern Hungary compared to state-of-the-art technology levels and solutions for the same applications identified via technology scouting.

Identifying the technology gap allows the research teams to investigate sustainable, circular approaches via the lens of societal, company, economic, and policy perspectives. This will help inform on barriers to establishing a successful hub in the target region.

2.1. Document Scope

This report describes the preliminary working conditions, contents and members of the **CiRCLETECH** research hub. To define what a research hub is, we first describe and analyse several existing hubs to learn about important elements and structures for **CiRCLETECH** to adopt. After defining the elements of the research hub, we continue defining its research scope.

The research scope comprises four scientific topics as well as the development of management competencies. The universities collaboratively shaped the research topics, based on ongoing research, expertise, and gaps found in the literature. The report continues with defining the working principles that guide the operations of the interdisciplinary research teams, specifying the roles and responsibilities of the members, developing individual research plans, and communication schemes and file sharing. The report concludes with a procedure for onboarding new members to the research teams.

2.2. Methodology

This report makes use of several methods to start defining the research hub, its working principles and boundaries. As a first step, it relies on an analysis of existing hubs to learn from and get inspired by. Next, to shape the content of the research topics, it uses workshops and an iterative process for drafting one-pagers. For the development of the research communities, it makes use of a mix of networking events, like lunch meetings and presentations. And finally, for detailing the working principles of the research groups.

To get an understanding of what elements make up a successful research hub, we've analyzed existing research hubs based on desk research and information exchanges with those hub members to validate the contents of the collected information. Six hubs were selected for the analysis: all of which are connected to the research at the university within the partnership and related to sustainability and/ or circular economy. The selected hubs have varying maturity levels.

To draft one-pagers for each of the four research topics, we first organised a workshop to map the topics included in ongoing research at each of the three involved universities. The workshop process and tables generated as an outcome of the topic mapping are in Annex 1 of this document. The outcomes were digitized and shared within the research teams at UMIN to be further developed into one-pagers. The one-pagers were compiled collaboratively and reviewed by several researchers, before sharing them with the other two universities. As a next step, TUD and LUT reviewed the documents internally, to ensure align and to check the quality.

Figure 1: Impressions from the workshop

Different methods were used to recruit new members to the research teams from UMIN, TUD and LUT. The first step was to make a shared overview in an Excel document and make a long-list of potential candidates based on desk research, referred to as the directory. To do this, university websites, Google Scholar, and Research Gate were searched to find all circular economy and sustainability-related research fellows relating to the four research subtopics. Once the long list was created, the next step was to develop a slide deck to introduce the project and its need and benefits to potential new members, as well as a standardized e-mail which has been sent out to get new members interested and engaged. Events in the form of dinners, lunch meetings and presentations were organised to communicate the project to a broader audience. A mix of guests joined for the dinner: PhDs, postdocs, professors and managers (**figure 2**). The Excel file stored at the central **CIRCLETECH** MS Teams group was updated to keep track of the audience reached, their interest and their commitment.

Figure 2: Networking dinner to inform TU Delft researchers about CIRCLETECH

Another challenge was to set up the working principles, the group hierarchy, roles and responsibilities of involved individuals that are aligned with the project objectives, practical and realistic and consider available project resources. The first model for this was identified already in the proposal phase and that model was the Vision teams by TU Delft. Vision

Teams are efforts by TU Delft to learn about perspectives on technologies that exist in society. TU Delft is in the foreground of developing technologies and is informing society about these technologies and their uses. TU Delft is regularly creating vision teams, each for discussing with organisations, industry and the general public a particular technology or technology-related challenge contributing to solving global challenges with technologies, and it wants to participate and be available in societal discussions about technologies.

A vision team consists of TU Delft experts from different fields and different faculties. These experts explore the societal impact of a particular technology or challenge and organise meetings with stakeholders from industry, governance, and society for discussing perspectives, opportunities and concerns. Outcomes may range from shorter position statements to elaborate websites, for presenting technologies, giving scans of discussions in society about them, and offering visions of TU Delft.

Taking this approach modified a bit with the approach of existing, voluntary and informally organised international research groups – one example is this: <https://www.operator4.com/research-network>.

After taking stock of example models, a draft was created and circulated in different levels, of the partner organisations and adjusted with the project coordinator until the final version presented in this document was agreed upon consensually.

3. Background

3.1. Analysis of existing research hubs

To define and develop a successful sustainable circular research hub, three existing research hubs at the TU Delft were analysed to learn from and get inspired by. The descriptions below explain the aim and scope of the project, its unique strengths, as well as the audience they address. The end of this section contains the analysis of the hubs and learnings for developing the CiRCLETECH hub.

3.1.1. Delft University of Technology; Delft Circularity Initiative

The TU Delft research hub which is most directly linked to the hub envisioned in this project is the Delft Circularity Initiative (DCI). The purpose of the DCI is to connect all circular economy-related research activities and researchers within TU Delft, to create an overview of ongoing work, find alignment for collaboration and develop a coherent mission moving forwards. The main aim of the DCI is to support TU Delft's leadership in circular economy-related research and to guide the societal transition towards a circular economy. Participants in the hub include researchers and coordinators from each of the eight Faculties at TU Delft: Aerospace; Applied Sciences; Architecture; Civil Engineering; Computer Science; Industrial Design Engineering; Mechanical, Maritime, and Materials Engineering; and Technology, Policy, and Management. Meetings are ad-hoc but are organized around upcoming grant calls, knowledge exchange opportunities, and strategy development. Workshops and meetings have involved identifying current ongoing research to create a network map of individuals and topic areas, matchmaking for upcoming grants, science communication strategies, and discussions regarding the vision and goals of the group. There is a core group of individuals who help organize meetings and identify upcoming opportunities which may benefit hub members (e.g. grant calls, conferences, and opportunities to showcase research). Future ambitions of the DCI include identifying opportunities to better showcase research outcomes to the external world, engaging policy makers to inform and shape national and international policies, collaboratively developing on and off-line education for both students and professionals, and publishing collaborative outcomes from the hub in scientific journals.

The strengths of this hub are the presence of interdisciplinary researchers with in-depth knowledge of developing technological innovations for products, equipment and systems with sustainable circular impacts. Expertise ranges from fundamental science to engineering and design, involving highly technical methods (e.g. photovoltaic cell components and materials) as well as user-centred approaches (e.g. co-creation and citizen science). Members of the hub intend to use their strong social links and intention to take long time horizons into account to contribute to impactful societal transitions with the support of the hub.

The audience the hub aims to address and share knowledge and create awareness with consists of global scientific communities, university students, and governmental bodies (e.g. national, international, local)

- Established in: 2021
- The hub is led by: Tillmann Klein, Jaco Quist, Gijsbert Korevaar, Cornelis van de Kamp, Jan-Henk Welink, Yumiko Hennebery, Olga Ioannou, David Peck
- Meeting frequency is: Once every two months
- Communication channel(s): Internal documents, slide decks, presentations

3.1.2. Delft University of Technology; Circular Built Environment hub

The Circular Built Environment hub (CBE) is an initiative within the Faculty of Architecture & the Built Environment at the TU Delft and has 70 members. This hub centres around knowledge development and exchange to help make the designs of future buildings, cities and infrastructures circular. The intention for this hub is to align and map all cross-department activities and structure them using key themes. They've formulated the following definition: "A Circular Built Environment is a human-made environment that operates according to circularity principles. Thus, CBE is a designed system aiming to close resource loops at different spatial-temporal scales to enable the society to thrive within the planetary boundaries."

The strengths of this hub are its presence on different scales and topics related to the circular-built environment. They zoom in on parts and components, but also evaluate circular performance on the level of assemblies or materials. At a larger scale, they look at resource flows in areas, districts and beyond. Their research focuses on technological innovations, new design approaches, and innovative management models within these scales. This layered scope asks for multidisciplinary collaborations and well as including stakeholder perspectives and management.

Figure 3: Circularity multidisciplinary

The hub therefore not only addresses students and employees of the TU Delft, but also relevant stakeholders at the previously mentioned scales. Similar to the CDI hub, the CBE hub makes use of on and off-line learning modalities to educate those interested.

- Website: www.tudelft.nl/CircularBE
- Established in: 2017
- The hub is led by: Tillmann Klein
- The meeting frequency is: once a month
- Communication channel(s): Website, newsletter, LinkedIn, faculty and university websites

3.1.3. Delft University of Technology; Sustainable campus

The sustainable campus initiative has the aim to make the campus operates fully sustainably by 2030. This means that it operates in a carbon-neutral and circular way while being climate adaptive and adding to the quality of life of the campus and exposing its excellence and sustainable character. For this initiative, sustainability is regarded most broadly, not only looking at the buildings and building facility, but it also links to how people move within the campus, what energy systems are adopted, as well as its flora and fauna and accompanied biodiversity, not to forget the resource and waste streams.

Educational programs offered at TU are made up of a fixed part, containing the fundamental and required basic knowledge for a discipline, but also have the flexibility to respond to trends and developments. Sustainability gets ingrained into this flexible part more and more, as the topic has gained increased attention over the decades. While the offer is being continuously improved, circularity, climate adaptation and nature-based design have become common topics in the courses throughout all programs. Besides, research groups focusing on sustainable topics are growing and national and international research projects on related topics have received significant amounts of funding.

Strategies and roadmaps guide the transition towards a fully sustainable campus. Through data collection and analysis, a baseline was created for the starting point of the initiative. Careful monitoring and reporting help track the progress of making the needed adjustments and getting the required innovations installed.

This initiative is directed at every single person, as well as other living beings, who make us the campus or have a relation to the campus.

- Website: <https://www.tudelft.nl/en/sustainability>
- Established in: 2021
- The hub is led by: Andy van den Dobbelsteen
- The meeting frequency is: once a month
- Communication channel(s): Website

3.1.4. University of Miskolc; Centre of Excellence for Sustainable Natural Resources Management at UNIM

The mission of the Centre of Excellence for Sustainable Natural Resources Management for nearly a decade is the educational and research activities supporting sustainable natural resource management. In the framework of project TÁMOP-4.2.1.B-10/2/KONV-2010-0001 intensive research work was carried out with the collaboration of researchers and lecturers from different faculties of the university to achieve the objectives of the European Council. The European Council precisely formulated the goal in the strategy of sustainable development in 2006. According to the document, sustainable development means that the needs of the present generation should be met without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. In line with the previous objective is the overall objective of the Treaty of the European Union, which controls all the policies and activities of the Union.

Its essence is to maintain the biodiversity of the Earth, democracy, gender equality, solidarity, the rule of law and respect for fundamental rights, including an understanding of freedom and equality for all.

It aims to continuously improve the quality of life and well-being of the community in the countries for the present and future generations. Sustainable development will facilitate dynamic economic development, full employment and a high level of education, healthcare, social and territorial cohesion and environmental protection in a peaceful and secure world, respecting cultural diversity.

The Scientific Workshops of the Centre of Excellence for Sustainable Natural Resources Management led by the Faculty are recognized at an international level are the follows:

- **Raw Materials Management**
primary and secondary raw materials exploration, mining, preparation technology development, mining and industrial waste processing, metal bearing waste processing, waste management, environmental legal analysis
 - **Energy management**
biomass, geothermal, renewable gas, carbon-dioxide storage, biomass Social Sciences
 - **Geo-information processing**
inversion methods, spectral and geoelectric methods, the development of numerical methods for geological, petrographic mineral development numerical methods, surveying and GIS methods, geo-economic line
 - **Water Resources Management**
innovative water management, protection of groundwater resources, hydrodynamic and transport modelling, geophysical exploration methods of water
- Established in: 2017
 - The CC is led by: Péter Szűcs
 - The meeting frequency is: task and opportunity-driven
 - Communication channel(s): University website

3.1.5. University – Business cooperation centre on Advanced Materials and Smart Technologies

Establishment of Advanced Materials and Smart Technologies (FIEK) at the University of Miskolc (GINOP-2.3.4.-15-2016-00004) project, the consortium members (horizontal dimension) are the BorsodChem Zrt., Robert Bosch Energy and Body Systems, Starters E-Components Generators Automotive (S.E.G.A. Hungary), ÉMI Construction Quality Control Innovation Non-profit Ltd and led by the University of Miskolc. (UMIN). The project/FIEK identifies three focus areas or sub-projects as the scope of RDI tasks: advanced materials and their testing; advanced materials technologies; intelligent control and automation. The first two areas build on each other synergistically and allow for complementary research in line with the partners' direct RDI themes. The third area links the two basic dimensions and also offers the possibility for independent activities in the framework of Industry 4.0 research. The selected focal points provide the technical background for R and D activities from basic and applied research to market deployment.

- Established in: 2017
- The centre is led by: Béla Viskolcz
- The meeting frequency: task and opportunity-driven
- Communication channel(s): University website

3.1.6. LUT University; Platform SCI-MAT Sustainable circularity of inorganic materials

The SCI-MAT platform meets the inorganic raw material needs of industry, taking social, environmental, and economic sustainability into consideration. Metals and industrial minerals have increasing significance in societies, as they are needed in modern technologies. The circularity of critical metals and other kinds of inorganic raw materials is essential for sustainable development towards carbon neutrality. Many of the metals used in modern technologies are scarce and the primary resources are often localized. Adding to the challenge, these local resources may be in areas where their utilization carries significant ethical and/or political issues.

- Established in: 2021
- The centre is led by: Sami Virolainen
- The meeting frequency: task and opportunity-driven
- Communication channel(s): University website

3.1.7. Conclusions of existing hubs

The descriptions of the four hubs from the three universities indicate what objectives existing hubs have and what elements the hubs are made up of. This informs what are important elements for the **CIRCLETECH** hub to structure, adopt and develop. The first component is to have a clear mission relevant to the particular hub that will be co-created by the four research groups and formulated in D2.3- Strategy on joint research activities. The mission should demonstrate awareness of, and a strong connection to, all relevant stakeholders will be formulated in D4.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan including the project website. The existing hubs very clearly built upon the strengths of the respective partners and build on already established processes, instead of solely building new processes from the ground up. It seems important to know the current activities, their quality, and structures, as they form the starting point for the development of the new hub. The Delft hubs have a clear aim and sense of direction. Not only is the starting point clear, but the end goals are also defined, and some hubs even monitor the progress carefully to ensure a good quality transition. Having the starting point, end point and monitoring parameters defined can help in establishing a world-class hub in Miskolc.

4. Research scope and teams

4.1. Research objective and scope of CiRCLETECH

When the partners formulated the research objectives for the **CiRCLETECH** project, the baseline assumption was that research capacity to build within the framework of the program shall address the industrial challenges of the region where UNIM is located and be built upon the competencies already existing at UNIM. The S3 strategy is not available at the regional level in Hungary, however, the Hungarian S3 strategy identifies several challenges that are identical in the industrialised Northern Hungarian region. The region itself home to the manufacturing industry, mostly as part of the automotive industry value chain as well as a prominent chemical industry is present. The mountainous part of the region is rich in industrial minerals therefore mining and mineral commodity production is also major factor.

Manufacturing accounted for 22.2% of gross value added (GVA) on average in the ten years following the 2008 crisis, and its share increased in a dominant trend until 2015 when it still accounted for 24%. In 2019, the manufacturing sector accounted for only 20.9% of GVA although its production volume increased year on year between 2009 and 2019 (KSH).

The manufacturing sector is also a major export earner: the share of exports in sales (at current prices) averaged 74.0% between 2015 and 2019 (KSH, 2020). Vehicle manufacturing is a key sector within the manufacturing industry. The role of the automotive industry should also be emphasised because it can also stabilise other industries (e.g. iron and metal, electronics or another mechanical engineering), contributing to Hungary's role as a regional centre not only for vehicle assembly but also for the production of automotive components (Irinnyi Plan, 2016, pp 54-55). The Hungarian Industry 4.0 Platform (Industry 4.0 Platform, 2020) has revealed that half of the companies surveyed on the impact of Industry 4.0 expect automation to reduce the number of full-time employees (Fülep, Nick and Várgedő, 2018). A problem in preparing for industrial transformation is that the skills of employees and managers are not high enough to ensure effective business practices (e.g. digitisation) (country report 2019). This problem was identified as a bottleneck to the spread of innovation in the design of the smart specialisation strategy. The Irinyi Plan (2016) identifies the food, textiles and wood and construction industries as less knowledge-intensive sectors, while the knowledge-intensive sectors that employ more highly skilled workers are the ICT sector, chemicals and especially pharmaceuticals.

The circular economy is a centre element of the UNIM research strategy with long research history, therefore in line with the above-mentioned challenges and industrial specificities identified by the S3 strategy of Hungary, the research objective of the **CiRCLETECH** project is to identify the level of sustainable technologies currently used by the companies operating in Northern Hungary by actively reaching out for them and involving them into the project activities through the existing territorial Innovation Platforms¹ and comparing them to state-of-the-art technology level and solutions for the same applications identified via technology scouting in more advanced European region and find solutions to enhance both technological and social innovation to increase the innovativeness of the region

¹ <https://nkfih.gov.hu/for-the-applicants/territorial-innovation-platforms>

4.2. Subtopic 1 - Urban and waste mining, material recycling

Research Group Leader: **Dr. József Fatil** (UMIN)
Research Group Advisor: **Dr. Antti Hakinen** (LUT)

4.2.1. Research objective and scope

The resources which are contained in wastes should be recovered and utilised as much as possible because of the following issues: concern about increasing global consumption of non-renewable resources, progressive shortages of primary raw materials, reduction of space available for final disposal of wastes, the need for quantity and volume reduction of wastes generated, the need for control of environmental contamination caused by emissions from waste treatment, changing social attitudes towards waste management, etc. (Cossu & Williams 2015). According to Cossu and Williams (2015), the terminology **Landfill Mining** represents the activities involved in extracting and processing wastes which have been previously stocked in particular kinds of deposits (municipal landfills, mine tailings, etc.). **Urban Mining** extends landfill mining to the process of reclaiming compounds and elements from any kind of anthropogenic stocks, including buildings, infrastructure, industries, products (in and out of use), and environmental media receiving anthropogenic emissions. The stocked materials may represent a significant source of resources, with concentrations of elements often comparable to or exceeding natural stocks. A definition distinguishing between “stock” and “flow” resources, either anthropogenic or natural, may be necessary. Annual stocks of materials held in geological deposits, groundwater reservoirs, household and industrial buildings, infrastructure and scrap products may not vary much over time. However, annual flows of materials may change considerably from year to year, depending upon the prevailing economic situation, fashion, technical innovations, etc. Nevertheless, from both anthropogenic stock and flow resources, secondary raw materials are produced. **Resource Recovery** includes the energy that can be generated by treating and managing wastes as well as materials recycling. **Materials Recycling** aims to transform selected wastes into materials that can be used in the manufacture of new products. Packaging waste (plastics, paper, cans, glass), putrescible, bottom ash, sewage, exhausted oils, scrap tyres, WEEE, end-of-life vehicles etc., are waste flows commonly considered as falling within material recycling strategies. The recovered materials after processing (not necessarily implying an extraction process) are reintroduced in production cycles. The extraction and processing of materials during urban mining are strongly based on economic feasibility. However, in some current material recycling strategies, political and social issues may drive recycling practices, sometimes inappropriately, either by following ideologies or by excluding technical options based on negative public opinions.

Therefore, the **Urban and waste mining research subtopic** focuses on the technical and scientific as well as the social awareness development of materials recovery, materials recycling and resource recovery of anthropogenic stock and flow types of resources. Research is based on the existing knowledge and experience of the partner Universities as the starting point and further seeking new applications and target material streams. Recent focus areas as starting points are the followings. The social and economic aspects of urban mining including the investigation and development of public awareness of waste management and circular economy, the growth, investment and new start-ups of the field and mapping and using of artificial intelligence for this aim. Another group of research interests is related to the material sciences, such as the applied material analytical methods (microstructure analysis) of urban mining, material and recycling technologies development from the point of view of urban mining in buildings, cars, batteries, ceramics and polymers, glass foams, municipal solid wastes, magnets and motor components, etc. Another group of research interests is related to the sampling, mapping and discovery of potential waste and landfill mining resources including municipal solid waste landfills, mine and energetic waste

and by-product deposits, tailing ponds and other urban stock and flow types of resources. And the last subject area, - which is realized in cooperation with the **Materials recycling research subtopic** - is focused on the examination of processing techniques and technologies for producing commodity materials for downstream manufacturing.

Contribution to SDG9: Industry, innovation, and infrastructure

4.3. Subtopic 2 - Processing technologies in waste recycling

Research Group Leader: **Dr. Sándor Nagy** (UNIM)

Research Group Advisor: **Dr. Teemu Kinnarinen** (LUT)

4.3.1. Research objective and scope

The European Commission has adopted a new Circular Economy Action Plan – one of the main blocks of the European Green Deal, Europe's new agenda for sustainable growth. The new Action Plan announces initiatives along the entire life cycle of products, targeting for example their design, promoting circular economy processes, fostering sustainable consumption, and aiming to ensure that the resources used are kept in the EU economy for as long as possible. Waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) or e-waste is electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) that becomes waste. High-added-value products usually require special materials, and without them, production is not possible (e.g.: indium in LCDs). Nowadays some important raw materials mainly come from non-European countries, for example, Rare Earth Elements (REE) from China.

The amount of electrical and electronic equipment put on the market in the EU evolved from 7.6 million tonnes in 2012 to a peak of 12.4 million tonnes in 2020 (over the period 2012-2020). The total collected WEEE increased from 3.0 to 4.7 million tonnes in the same period (EUROSTAT). The amount of WEEE is generally increasing because of the intensification of technological developments, increasing population, rapid societal and economic development (developing countries access to modern technologies), and changes in consumer habits (mobile phones, decreasing product lifetimes). On the one hand, untreated WEEE is hazardous to the environment and human health; on the other hand, WEEE is a resource which should be used.

WEEE processing faces many challenges, e.g. extremely small concentrations of valuable elements, composite materials, thin layers, covering materials, rapid changes in EEE technologies, the substitution of elements, and market price variation of elements.

Collection, material recycling and energetically utilisation of municipal solid waste is also a considerable task nowadays.

Our research group focuses on the following material flows, and waste flows:

- E-mobility and mobility (auto parts, sensors, electronic parts, PCBs, plastic);
- E-mobility (LiBs, parts of drive train);
- WEEE (high-tech equipment, LED, displays, PCB);
- Municipal solid wastes (processing, RDF/SRF production);

and on the following research areas:

- Processing technologies in waste recycling;
- Pre-processing and processing;
- Mechanical separation;

- Separation techniques
- Advanced separation technologies;
- Critical raw materials recovery;
- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)
- Waste and flue gas analysis, heat transfer;
- Logistics, mechatronics, Industry 4.0 technologies, robotics.

Contribution to SDG 9: Industry, innovation, and infrastructure and SDG 12: Responsible consumption and production

4.4. Subtopic 3 - Circular manufacturing

Research Group Leader: **Dr. Gabriella Vadászné Bognár** (UNIM)

Research Group Advisor: **Dr. David Peck** (TUD)

4.4.1. Research objective and scope

Current production and consumption patterns of materials, products, and services in a linear economy follow the operational process of a 'take–make–dispose of,' economy, which causes widespread inefficiencies in the value chain over the entire lifecycle: starting from resource extraction and product design to End-of-Life disposal. Profitability is the primary focus of a linear economy which puts increased pressure on finite resources, and environmental and social sustainability. Furthermore, two critical problems arise from the linear production and consumption practices: (1) limited scope for resource recovery due to product design which only considers a single use-cycle and (2) non-regenerative activities within our ecosystem which slowly deplete our natural resources.

As natural resources and the Earth's capacity to absorb waste are limited, it is important to reduce dependence on natural resources by decoupling production growth from consumption. In the long term, resources are finite, which means that we will not be able to 'take' as much as we want or need. On the other hand, the Earth's capacity to dissipate waste is also finite, which means that we will not be able to "throw it away" as we want or need to. So, one side of the challenge is closing material loops, and the other side is eliminating waste. Although closing material loops means a continuous effort in the manufacturing environment. In a traditional manufacturing company, this effort is limited to the manufacturing processes to minimise costs and waste. Manufactured products often carry a significant amount of remaining functional life at end-of-use/end-of-life (EoU/EoL) and manufacturers typically do not address their conservation or recovery. Research and industrial practices, such as remanufacturing, have shown that there is huge economic and environmental potential for recovering the value of products in their EoU/EoL state.

The focus of the **subtopic Circular manufacturing** (CM, hereafter) is on the potential to introduce circular production systems in which profitability and environmental sustainability can be maintained simultaneously without compromise. Despite the proven economic and environmental benefits, successful examples of circular systems are still few and far between. Systems thinking and systematic approaches to managing industries are important, as are analytical methods and tools that can be used to assess different aspects of circular production systems. The main aspects will be on the adaptation to industrial implementation of the methods and conceptual frameworks that are essential for the implementation of circular manufacturing systems.

It is estimated that the adaptation of the CM approach can yield material cost savings of hundreds of billions of dollars per year for the EU and can result in huge environmental benefits. To tap this potential, the manufacturing industry needs to take a circular approach, where the products are **designed intentionally to be used for multiple lifecycles**. Since 2009, the Ecodesign Directive has aimed to enhance the security of supply and contribute to sustainable development by establishing a framework for setting **ecodesign requirements** for energy-related products (ErPs, i.e. products that use or have an indirect impact on energy

consumption). The majority of the implementing measures set out so far under the Ecodesign Directive regulate energy efficiency at the use phase, but as the energy efficiency of ErPs is considered with the implementation of this policy, the environmental impacts associated with other stages of the environmental life cycle have become relatively more significant.

CM is a core mechanism for realizing a circular economy. To design an effective CM system, it is necessary to evaluate different **life cycle scenarios** in terms of their economic and environmental performance. The researchers will focus on life cycle scenarios which represent how products, modules, parts, and materials (collectively called items hereafter) are circulated employing life cycle options, which are methods (such as reuse and recycling) to reduce resource consumption and environmental load. Another research topic is the life cycle management of components machined in mass production and the use of sustainable and renewable raw materials; consumer awareness; and the design, use, and **manufacturing of sustainable, recyclable, reusable, and repairable products, components, and materials.**

The emergence of **new advanced manufacturing technologies** creates opportunities for changing how manufacturing activities are organised. Alongside important advances in innovation processes, technologies may affect the distribution of manufacturing and the subsequent flow of materials and goods with many potential sustainability benefits.

One such advanced technology is **3D printing** (also known in the industry as additive manufacturing). Industrial applications of 3D printing are enabling more circular production systems with the use of recycled and reclaimed materials as input. We shall focus simultaneously on the implementation of recycling, repairing and the use of bio-based materials.

In the CM our area is a system of production and consumption which aims to maximize efficient use of resources and waste through closed-loop, regenerative and shared approaches, and at the same time, avoids unnecessary consumption of natural resources and the **optimization of processes and exchange of technologies**—consequently, reduction of costs”.

Recycling predominately focuses on the technical cycle, which supplies (recycled) materials to the parts manufacturers. Recycling is one of the critical paths of CM and directly connects with a group of researchers, such as waste collection, parts manufacturers, and users. A group of research interests is related to the design of recycling-related logistics solutions from sustainability, automated material handling and Industry 4.0 technology aspects. The reuse of materials and components built into machining industrial products is a topic of interest.

Contribution to SDG 7: Affordable and clean energy and to SDG 9: Industry, innovation, and infrastructure.

4.5. Subtopic 4 - Sustainable energy transition – Just transition

Research Group Leader: **Dr. Tekla Szép** (UNIM)

Research Group Advisor: **Dr. David Peck** (TUD)

4.5.1. Research objective and scope

The European Union launched the ‘Fit for 55’ package of policies seeking to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) by a net 55% by 2030. This is a mid-term goal toward implementing the EU’s Green Deal to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. Across all countries, the policy packages envision residential energy consumption to drop, facilitated by energy efficiency improvements and higher energy costs. Social welfare, in the form of the ‘Social Climate Fund’, may be given to those households living in energy and mobility poverty. The EU recently responded to the energy crisis brought about by Russia’s war in Ukraine with the REPowerEU, which accelerates the ambition of Fit for 55.

Measuring progress of the European Union toward the SDG7 (Affordable and clean energy), SDG11 (Sustainable cities and communities) and SDG13 (Climate action) a demonstrable perpetual weakness (spillover effects, ecological debt, insufficient progress regarding energy efficiency) in energy and climate issues is being addressed. Studies (LaBelle M. C. and Szép T. 2022; Sachs et al. 2019) show that many EU Member States were failing to improve their SDGs (with special regard to SDG7, SDG11 and SDG13) in 2019. For example, in the European Union the final energy consumption (TOE per capita) was higher in 2019 than in the prescribed 2020 targets adopted in 2012 (Eurostat, 2022). However, by 2020, Covid pushed the region further behind (LaBelle M. C. and Szép T. 2022; Szép T., Pálvölgyi T., Kármán-Tamus É. 2022). On the surface, the restrictions (curfews, promoting the home office, etc.) supported the efforts to achieve the 2020 energy and climate goals. But the long-term trends reveal that neither the European Union nor the Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) countries were on the right track to achieve SDG7, SDG11 and SDG13 in 2019 (before the pandemic hit). The slowing progress indicates the lack of political, economic, and social commitment, conflicts of interest, and the difficulties of decentralization processes. An unjust energy transition fails to deliver on the SDGs (and 2030 energy and climate goals) and reduces the resiliency of communities, leaving them exposed to future crises.

The *Sustainable energy transition research group* focuses on new policies that must be implemented. The failure to improve demonstrates the overall lack of progress in decoupling economic growth from energy consumption. Energy convergence and other inequalities (especially energy poverty) are still unresolved policy issues (LaBelle M.C., Tóth G., Szép T. 2022; Szép T., Tóth G., LaBelle M. C. 2022). There is a strong direct and indirect relationship (LaBelle M. C., Tóth G., Szép T. 2022; Szép T., Tóth G., LaBelle M. C. 2022) between residential energy consumption and human well-being that refer to higher vulnerability and lower resilience. A final goal of the policy efforts to build sustainable energy systems and improve the adaptability of (energy) communities and countries, is to enhance their resiliency during periods of crisis. Energy communities represent a new approach to energy democracy and energy justice. It also includes fair pay and the creation of green jobs supporting the just transition. Northern Hungary is one of the coal regions in transition that relies heavily on fossil fuels for energy use and greenhouse gas-intensive industries too.

Beyond energy policy research, other topics are also highlighted. The research group pays particular attention to the household sector which is hit hard by the energy crisis. In 2020, the household sector (the second-largest end-use sector after transport) was responsible for 27% of final energy consumption in the European Union (Eurostat, 2022). However, in the last decade, the vast energy efficiency potential in the household sector remained largely untapped (the long-term trend (2004-2019) shows moderate progress, and movement away from the EU target can be observed in the short term between 2014-2019), impairing global efforts to mitigate climate change (LaBelle M. C. and Szép T. 2022; Sachs et al. 2019.). The problem is exacerbated by the fact that the share of household primary solid biomass use in residential renewable energy consumption was 82.5% in 2020 in the European Union (Eurostat, 2023). CEE is stuck in a traditional biomass trap, and this together with the energy stacking theory shed light on the slow progress of the energy transition in the household sector (Szép T., Pálvölgyi T., Kármán-Tamus É. 2023). Regarding household activities, heating decarbonization is the key to reducing energy poverty and increasing resilience. Smart cities and smart energy (smart appliances, smart metering) represent a new strand of research.

Beyond the social and economic aspects, energy innovation and technological improvements are also needed. Our core areas are:

- possibilities for a sustainable campus;
- grid-scale energy storage;
- decentralized energy production and island operation;
- community heating;
- grid immunity and stability, energy security issues;
- computational design of electrochemical processes;

- circular carbon economy: emission, GHG storage, capturing, products from CO₂;
- design of biomass-based chemical feedstocks and chemical energy carriers using computational chemistry;
- ammonia-based chemical industry and energy economy;
- computational electrochemistry;
- alternative ways of hydrogen production:
 - carbon and mineral resource assessment;
 - examination of technological solutions for carbon-based hydrogen production;
 - Blending (use 'replacing') hydrogen into the natural gas network;
 - investigate of hydrogen - natural gas and synthetic gas turbines ???;
 - LCOE (levelized cost of energy) studies.

5. Coordination, communication and operational processes

The creation of an operating framework of joint research helps to set up the basis of long-lasting research cooperation in the field of Sustainable Circular Economy. This will enable the detailing of joint research ideas and help the uptake of technological research results in the area. The creation of the **CIRCLETECH** Hub will not only result in a regional excellence centre but will also increase involvement in Horizon Europe programmes as the implementation of a European research strategy.

The aim is to connect technological and socioeconomic research activities in the field of sustainable circular economy to boost research excellence and management capacity of the partner universities - Establishing multidisciplinary dynamic research teams in the four subtopics, that will develop responses to the practical question of connecting technological innovation with socio-economic research. Teams will work in interaction with each other compiling a set of measures and solutions for real take-up of technological innovations and their integration into the circular economy, with a particular interest in the materials flow of industrial cycles.

RESEARCH GROUP – Objectives, Structure and Tasks

Objectives: To perform research under the four topics aligned with EU policies, Horizon Europe work programmes, produce the deliverables and achieve project KPIs according to the Action Plan

Structure on how these objectives will be reached.

- Research groups will be built in the four topics including researchers from all partners (Matrix) under the coordination of WP2 Leader (David Peck)
- Research groups will be led by the Research Group Leaders from UMIN supported by their advisor counterparts, a Group Advisor either from TUD or LUT – They will help define the objectives of the group, quantify the goals and define the performance indicators for the research group, manage activities and control performance
- Local group coordinators will manage the work of the research team at the level of Partner institutions and report to the Research Group leaders according to the internal working procedures of the group.
- Researchers from UM will develop their development plan (IDP), under the monitoring of the local group coordinators and guided by the internal protocols of the research team. Researchers from TUD and LUT may voluntarily be doing research based on their research interests.

Tasks to be performed by the research groups:

- Formulate new research ideas and strategies
- Identify calls and write Horizon Europe and other proposals
- Deliver publications (joint and individual)
- Involve students to research work and supervise them
- Perform dissemination and exploitation activities of research results
- Build professional partnerships
- Carry out inter-organizational mobility, research gap identification and ideation workshops
- Deliver
 - D2.1 - Multidisciplinary cross-organizational research teams
 - D2.2 - Expert visits and research gap identification workshop
 - D2.3 - Strategy for joint research activities
 - D2.4 - Actions report for increasing CE technology adsorption and innovation capacity in the Northern Hungarian region

- D3.3 - Participant's individual development action plan based on training and mobility
- D4.3 - Report on Summer Schools
- and D4.4 - Joint MOOC on Circular Economy

5.1. Working principles of the research teams

CiRCLETECH research teams are jointly created by the **CiRCLETECH** consortium to learn about perspectives and further develop technologies that contribute to creating and maintaining Sustainable Circular Economy for all. With **CiRCLETECH**'s multi-organisational, multi-disciplinary research teams, we want to explore how technology uptake can be influenced and increased, as well as foster socio-techno-ecologic development in all three involved regions by creating the **CiRCLETECH HUB**.

CiRCLETECH's multidisciplinary research teams for discussing with organisations, industry and the general public sustainable circular economy-related challenges. All such teams consist of experts from different fields and from different organisations within the consortium being rather open to including professionals from industries outside of the consortium and students at all levels of their professional development (BSc, MSc and PhD). The research groups autonomously explore the societal impact of any relevant and investigated technology or challenge, and organise meetings with stakeholders from industry, governance and society for discussing perspectives, opportunities and concerns. While doing joint research using mobility schemes, outcomes may range from shorter position statements to sharing views and findings in PodCasts and Meetups, presenting findings in joint research papers and presentations, reports and highlighting activities and findings in different news items. The basic principles set up for joint efforts are the following:

- 1) Each research group is an autonomously self-organising multidisciplinary team, consisting of researchers from all three organizations with diverse scientific backgrounds.
- 2) Each research team are led by an expert researcher from UNIM advised by a senior researcher from either LUT or TUD to leverage capacity building on their expertise, mindset, and experience to further grow the team members and also to foster impactful outcomes for society to benefit from.
- 3) Each research team develops and implements its working practices staying connected to its visions.
- 4) Research teams are open to recruiting new members and members are open to pro-actively integrating new researchers as well.
- 5) All activities supported by the **CiRCLETECH** Hub encourage the participation of researchers from all three institutions and any supported outcome and mobility have to involve researchers at least a UNIM researcher and a researcher from either LUT or TUD.
- 6) All activity leads to or contributes to the delivery of a submitted international project proposal, deliverables, KPIs or any other activities and results (Involving student in research work and supervising her/him, MOOC, workshops, Summer School, Podcasts and MeetUps, media events) and is in line with the thematic field of the research group where the researcher is involved.

5.1.1. Roles and responsibilities

RESEARCH GROUP LEADER

Research groups will be led by the **Research Group Leaders**. They will define the objectives of the group, quantify the goals, define the performance indicators for the research group, manage activities and control performance.

WHO? A **senior researcher** her/himself coordinating a thematic research group at the project level. *Research Group leaders are nominated by UNIM.*

TASKS and RESPONSIBILITIES:

- Defining the vision and objectives of the research group
- Defining qualitative and quantitative goals to be reached by the group
- Defining internal protocols of the research group and scheduling activities, deadlines
- Fostering cooperation within the group while inspiring its members
- Facilitating the strategy and ideation workshops
- Drafting the relevant deliverables with the support of the local group coordinators
- Ensuring the match and synergies between the group competencies, identified industry or societal challenges and funding opportunities
- Reporting to the WP2 leader with the support of the Local group coordinators
- Identifying thematic topics and experts within the network to deliver training (in the form of training, and meetups?) with the support of the local group coordinator.

Additional Tasks at UNIM

- Managing available research budget at UNIM deciding on how it's spent locally, maximizing the impact of the project
- Organizing skills and competency evaluation of the researchers in her/his group locally and together with the researchers defining, agreeing on and drafting Individual development plans (IDP)

- Based on IDPs, they create a research group plan (RGP) forecasting the work to be done, mobility to be expected, envisioned results, outcomes and KPIs to be delivered promptly – executing institutional RGPs to contribute to research Group objectives
- At UNIM, monitor the researcher's progress against her/his IDP and report to the researcher's dean and WP2 leader.

RESEARCH GROUP ADVISOR

Research group advisors support and mentor the Research Group Leaders to achieve their objectives. Research Group Advisors are delegated by either TUD or LUT.

WHO? A **senior researcher** her/himself well-established expert on the thematic field supporting a thematic research group at the project level by advising, mentoring and consulting the research Group Leader

TASKS and RESPONSIBILITIES are to support the research Group Leaders in achieving their objectives by supporting them on the:

- defining the vision and objectives of the research group
- defining qualitative and quantitative goals to be reached by the group
- defining internal protocols of the research group and scheduling activities, deadlines
- fostering cooperation within the group while inspiring its members
- facilitation of the strategy and ideation workshops
- drafting the relevant deliverables with the support of the local group coordinators
- ensure match and synergies between the group competencies, identified industry or societal challenges and funding opportunities
- reporting to the WP2 leader with the support of the Local group coordinators
- identifying thematic topics and experts within the network to deliver training with the support of the local group coordinator

LOCAL GROUP COORDINATOR

Local group coordinators will support the work of the research team at the level of Partner institutions and report to the Research Group leaders.

WHO? Is a junior researcher her/himself supporting the research groups at an institutional level

TASKS and RESPONSIBILITIES:

- Supporting the activities of the researchers at the institutional level cooperating with the Research Group leader, contributing to the deliverables and KPIs
- Supporting the Research Group Leader in organizing strategy and ideation workshops
- Working on the vision as well as the strategy documents that are deliverables together and by the coordination of the Research Group Leader
- Act as an information bridge between the local research group and the research group leader, providing and receiving information on international events, internal events (workshops, podcasts, meetups, etc..) funding opportunities
- Sharing information and invitation to the researchers on training, workshops, meetups and funding opportunities
- Managing available research budget and deciding on how it's spent locally maximizing the impact of the project (TUD and LUT only)

Additional TASKS and RESPONSIBILITIES at UNIM

- Supporting the research Group Leader on IDP and RDP development, evaluation, monitoring and implementation.
- Collecting news items from researchers and transfers to the project communications team
- Local coordinators are to update each other, coordinate activities between the research groups and inform/update the **CiRCLETECH** project coordinator

RESEARCHERS

Researchers will be selected for the programme voluntarily and take part in the research activities of the team under the leadership of the Research Group Leader.

TASKS AND RESPONSIBILITIES:

- Actively and proactively participate in ideation and strategy workshops.
- Actively and proactively seek opportunities to secure research grants and funds for her/his research.
 - Actively writing proposals with the support of the research management team
- Doing research with fellow researchers jointly from partner organizations (UNIM, TUD, LUT and involved industry)
 - Writing joint articles with a researcher from partner organizations (UNIM, TUD, LUT and involved industry) and publishing in papers or at conferences
 - Involving and supervising students in her/his research locally
 - In case of relevance, preparing and submitting IP protection requests on research findings

Additional TASKS AND RESPONSIBILITIES for UNIM researchers:

- They will undergo a skills and competency evaluation and define and formulate her/his Individual Development Plan agreed upon with the Research Group Leader
- Take part in training activities where gaps identified by the skills and competency evaluation and defined in the IDP
- Reporting to and evaluating her/his progress against the IDP to the Research Group Leader
- Document activities and proactively provide content for news items (task done, achievements, photos, videos) to *UM Local Group Coordinator*
- Offering content to Podcasts, Meetups and the MOOC based on her/his research and activity experience.

BENEFITS OFFERED BY THE PROGRAMME TO RESEARCHERS:

- Publishing costs of her/his joint paper, conference participation and travel costs of presenting her/his joint paper at an international conference are covered by the program
- Mobility to partner organizations is supported by the program (For UM researchers, in agreement with the Research Group Leader in line with the IDP)
- Guidance, mentoring and support for her/his project proposal and project from the idea to the closure by the research management team
- Training on skills and competency development

RESEARCH MANAGEMENT TEAM

Research management staff will support the work of the research teams with the following activities:

- Scout, cluster funding opportunities and inform the research group leaders and local coordinators
- Actively and proactively participate in ideation and strategy workshops contributing to an effective outcome
- Advise, support and mentor researchers on proposal idea generation, proposal writing, admin process and project implementation
- Policy review, best practices transfer
- Managing projects, mentoring
- Creating and organizing soft skills development and research management training

Capacity-building activities reinforcing the research management knowledge and capacities of UNIM will be reinforced in cooperation with the partner institutions. Focused training and mentoring will help the development of existing staff and the identification of gaps and needs of new capacities.

5.1.2. Individual Development Plans – IDP

An individual development plan will be drafted by each UM researcher involved voluntarily. The IDP serves the goal to provide a plan and vision on how the activities contribute to their individual growth as a researcher and how the lessons learnt will be used for this purpose. Individual development plans can be used to track progress and could potentially serve as a basis of service for UNIM researchers for supporting them to become full potential researchers.

Translating the above into practice, each researcher undergoes an evaluation taking relevant skills and competencies in stock to draw the baseline of the researcher's current status. After having the skills and competency evaluation results at hand, taking the career stage where the respective researcher is at, they shall create a vision of where the very same researcher would like to be/expected to be in 3 years – It shall be always demonstrating some sort of progress, for example, defending their PhD, becoming associate professor, habilitation, professorship, progress on Performance evaluation, etc...

An IDP is a descriptive document shortly describing the researcher's current status, the skills and competence evaluation results, and their vision and plan for where they would like to be in 3 years. It includes what actions the researcher would like to undertake. These actions are up to the researcher; however some actions are supported by the **CIRCLETECH** project, namely – providing networking and the opportunity to raise the interest of other, well-established researchers or the opposite junior researchers' interest to cooperate and work with, covering publication fees, International conference participation costs, research costs (materials, small equipment's, research-related travel and purchase costs -e.g. sampling or lab service) and some activities, such as workshops and training are mandatory

Additionally, each IDP shall have at least 2 tailor-made achievements that fit the researcher's learning path, for example, the first international journal publication, first international conference presentation, first research project proposal submitted, first PhD supervision, having at least one or two new co-authors, 20% citation growth during the project implementation etc. These can be defined flexibly and freely by each researcher with the agreement of the Research Group Leader

IDPs are approved by the Research Group Leaders and the respective deans of each researcher. Research Group Leaders individually negotiate the IDPs with the researchers. Each IDP combined must deliver all the KPIs, deliverables and results foreseen by the project, therefore Research Group Leaders must be negotiating well and allocate the budget accordingly. The Research Group Leaders must coordinate IDP drafting efforts among each other. Deans are involved with reason to be informed about their faculty member's involvement in the development program so they can incentivize, monitor and make faculty HR-related forecasts.

The involved UM researchers must have an IDP – participating in workshops upon request of Research Group Leaders; take part in training that is defined by the Research Group Leaders based on the initial skills and competency evaluation. This is a minimum criterion to be eligible for incentives offered by the Faculty deans.

By combining IDPs, an institutional-level **Research Group Plan** is created that aggregately contains all the planned activities, results, KPIs and individually defined achievements that help Local Group Coordinators coordinate activities, mobility and decide on budget spending - on mobility, publication, conference participation, other financial support for researchers in their group to achieve IDP and Group objectives. RGP will serve as D.3.3 - Participants' individual development action plan based on training and mobility.

List of KPIs foreseen by the CiRCLETECH project to reach within 3 years are*:

• Reach with MOOC	3000
• Researchers trained	20
• Staff exchanges carried out	>20
• Participation in personal grants, actions of UNIM researchers	3
• Innovative products or services concepts developed	4
• New research ideas by CiRCLETECH team	9
• Participation in Horizon Europe projects (UNIM)	8
• Joint Horizon Europe projects, submitted proposals	4
• R&D cooperation agreement with local stakeholders	5
• Intellectual property registrations UNIM	1
• Participation in national and international conferences	8
• joint research papers	5
• conference presentations	8
• Number of international students supervised	40

* Based on the proposal

Financial support is only provided to researchers' costs that are foreseen in their IDPs approved by the Research Group Leader and the respective dean and connected to activities that are also described in the IDP. It's the researcher's sole responsibility to by complying with the actual university policies manage the procurement and reporting of items that are subject to financial support.

5.2. Communication and File sharing platforms

According to the defined working principles of the research groups, especially principle 1) and 3), research groups are free and encouraged to define and implement practices in how they are keeping contact and communicating, and organising their work.

The major communication platform set up by the **CiRCLETECH** project management is a dedicated MS Teams group that each member of the research groups can use for communication (chat, video calls) and to store and jointly develop documents.

Each research group is mandatory to organise a research gap identification workshop (foreseen date latest 2023 July) to support the creation and delivery of D2.2 - Expert visits and research gap identification workshop (due date Month 10, 2023 July) and D2.3 Strategy

on joint research activities (due date Month 12, 2023 September) and at least two Design thinking workshops for idea generation and to promote design thinking (foreseen dates are 2023 December – 2024 January and 2024 June – July).

Decision-making mechanisms within the group and any other activities, including mobility plans, are to decide and develop by the research groups with a short description of activities and expected impact, decision-making processes and to inform the project management by an initial plan (due date is month 7 – 2023 April) and a quarterly report (short document) is expected to report progress by each research teams.

5.3. Recruitment and integration of new members

New members are welcome to apply by expressing interest in participation through an application system that will be available on the project website (foreseen date is Q3-Q4 2023) After the initial skills and competency evaluation is carried out, the newly volunteered researcher drafts her/his IDP jointly with the Research Group Leader. Based on the approved IDP, the researcher is involved in the **CIRCLETECH** Hub activities.

An *inauguration event* was organised at UNIM on the **20th of January 2023** where more than 60+ researchers and the research group leaders were present. Among the researchers, junior and senior researchers alike were invited already to the program and also researchers not yet engaged, but showed interest in the opportunity the program could offer. During the event, the **CIRCLETECH** project and the content of this document were introduced, and an engaged Q&A session was held.

Figure 4: Impressions from the inauguration event in UNIM, - 20/01/2023

6. Conclusions

The report begins with the analysis of six existing research hubs across all three **CIRCLETECH** partners. The descriptions of the six hubs from the three universities indicate what objectives existing hubs have and what elements the hubs are made up of. The existing hubs very clearly built upon the strengths of the respective partners. It was found to be important to have a clear mission relevant to the particular hub. It seems important to map the current activities, their quality, and structures, as they form the starting point for the development of the **CIRCLETECH** hub.

The Delft hubs have a clear aim and sense of direction. Not only is the starting point clear, but the end goals are also defined, and some hubs even monitor the progress carefully to ensure a good quality transition. Having the starting point, end point and monitoring parameters defined can help in establishing a world-class hub in Miskolc. Importantly the existing hubs showcase how sustainable, circular approaches via the lens of societal, companies, economic, and policy perspectives can be realized.

This report outlined the description of the four research topics by UMIN, LUT and TUD, identifying how those are connected to major European Strategies, and actions, to the strategic agenda of EIT RawMaterials and EIT Manufacturing and why this is important. This allows for the mapping, identification, and connection of the topics to the European Research and Innovation calls foreseen in 2023 and 2024 (HEU working programs for 2023-24). Building on the above, in the coming phases, the mapping, identification, and connection to relevant companies in the Northern Hungarian region and the other partner regions, will benefit from joining and cooperating with the research groups. This is essential in for example Horizon Europe calls, which increasingly seek company participation to demonstrate impact.

The creation of an operating framework of joint research helps to set up the basis of long-lasting research cooperation in the field of Sustainable Circular Economy. This will enable the detailing of joint research ideas and help the uptake of technological research results. The creation of the **CIRCLETECH** Hub will not only result in a regional excellence centre but will also increase involvement in Horizon Europe programmes as the implementation of a European research strategy. Equally the development of activities in the other two partner regions will help lift all.

The aim is to connect societal, companies, economic, and policy perspectives into our research activities in the field of sustainable circular economy, to boost the research excellence and management capacity of the partner universities. Establishing multidisciplinary dynamic research teams in the four subtopics will develop responses to the practical question of connecting technological innovation with socio-economic research.

Teams will work in interaction with each other compiling a set of measures and solutions, as described in the report for real take-up of technological innovations and their integration into the circular economy, with a particular interest in the materials flow of industrial cycles. An important measure is the KPIs, around education, research, mobility, and grants. Their performance and any new risks should be regularly reviewed and updated.

It is clear that the existing circular, sustainable actions taken by the partners in the **CIRCLETECH** project are robust and deliver meaningful impact. They provide a good base of knowledge and experience to build the four themes going forwards. By engaging with colleagues carefully, the impact and success of the four themes are heightened. The early stages of the **CIRCLETECH** project have ensured that the 'teams' aspect of the multidisciplinary, cross-organizational teams are robustly established. The next steps will be delivery and are guided by the coordination actions in Appendix 4.

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8. Annexes

8.1. Annexe 1 – Topic mapping during the kick-off meeting

Research subtopic #1: Urban and waste mining, material recycling

UM	LUT	TUD
Faculty of Economics (circular business models) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public awareness of the circular economy 	City of Lappeenranta Business school <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Growth Investments New start-up 	Faculty of Technology, Policy and Management (TPM) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mapping + AI Information systems
Faculty of Materials and Chemical Engineering <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI-AI recycling Municipal solid waste AI-AI: automated and building construction Buildings Cars Microstructure analysis Batteries Ceramics and polymers Glass foam recycling Hydrometallurgy Bio metallurgy 	Materials and chemical engineering <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI-AI recycling Municipal solid waste AI-AI: automated and building construction Microstructure analysis Batteries Ceramics and polymers Glass foam recycling Hydrometallurgy 	Faculty of Mechanical, Maritime and Materials Engineering (3ME) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ceramics and polymers Magnets and motor generation
Faculty of Earth Science and Engineering <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mining Tailings (incl. Fly ash) Mining waste spoil Geopolimersation Geopolymer foam Fibre stabilized geopolymer Municipal solid waste Automated sorting Handling Sensor Landfill mining 	Earth science and engineering <ul style="list-style-type: none"> New mind calibre Water permitting SLO Red mud filtering Mining Tailings Recovery value Bulk material use Geopolimersation Composites Replace concrete 3D print – infra noise barrier Urban infrastructure revolutions Water tech Electrocoagulation - toxic 	Faculty of Mechanical, Maritime and Materials Engineering (3ME) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geopolimersation Municipal solid waste

Research subtopic #2: Processing technologies in waste recycling

Advanced separation technologies, IT, Robotics, Logistics solutions, Big data, Machine learning, digital twin, simulator development, Process automation, process analytics, digitization

UM	LUT	TUD
Process technology waste recycling		
Pre-processing and processing		Faculty of Mechanical, Maritime and Materials Engineering (3ME)
E-mobility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Auto all • Batteries 		
(W)EEE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LTD • Sensors • PCBs • Plastics • Critical raw materials <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Copper ○ Indium ○ Tantalum • Municipal solid waste <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Separation techniques 	(W)EEE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal solid waste <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Separation techniques 	(W)EEE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal solid waste • Separation techniques • PLE recycling • Social action

Research subtopic #3: Circular manufacturing

UM	LUT	TUD
<p>Design – material reduction (2%)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmentally friendly design <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy ○ CO2 reduction ○ Recycling ○ Design for recycling 		
<p>Manufacturing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Auto Bosch • Mechatronics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Process robotics and sensors • LCS tools in production • PLE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Optimise costs in manufacturing ○ Assembly optimization ○ Regenerative design <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Machines tools ○ Refurbished parts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Remanufacturing? ○ 3D additive manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Design of composites 	<p>Manufacturing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3D additive manufacturing • Design of composites 	<p>Manufacturing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mechatronics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Process robotics and sensors • PLE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Assembly optimization ○ Lean remanufacturing • Regenerative design • Machines tools • 3D additive manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Design of composites
<p>Logistics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning, development, and optimization of CE production systems • Waste transport 	<p>Logistics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transportation of secondary materials 	<p>Logistics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning, development, and optimization of CE production systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ AI, Big data ○ Quantum blockchain ○ Material passports

Research subtopic #4: Sustainable energy transition – Just transition

UM	LUT	TUD
Social economic approach	Social economic approach	
Energy transition scoreboard (new)	Energy transition scoreboard (new) School of Engineering Science and Energy sustainability	
Move away from traditional biomass (firewood burning)		
Energy poverty <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Residential sector Core household activity: heating		Energy poverty <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Residential Heating
City level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart city and smart energy cities and systems Smart metering and smart appliances 		
Energy policy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Household sector Cities and regions RePOWEREU and Fit for SS Energy efficiency and regulated energy prices Scenario analysis (key) 	Energy policy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario analysis (key) 	Energy policy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Repower TU Fit 4 SS Scenario analysis (key)
Energy technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> grid-scale energy storage; decentralized energy production and island operation; grid immunity and stability; computational design of electrochemical processes; circular carbon economy; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> design of biomass-based chemical feedstocks and chemical energy carriers using computational chemistry; ammonia-based chemical industry and energy economy; 	Energy technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy storage – grid scale Decent energy generation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solar PV Heat pump 	Energy technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decent energy generation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solar PV Heat pump

<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ computational electrochemistry;○ alternative ways of hydrogen production:		
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8.2. Annexe 2 – Members of the research groups

Topic	First name	Last name	Organisation	Faculty	Title
Research subtopic #1: Urban and waste mining, material recycling	David	Peck	TUD	Architecture and the Built Environment	Full/ associate professor
	Benjamin	Sprecher	TUD	Industrial Design Engineering	Full/ associate professor
	Esther	van der Voet	Leiden University	Industrial Ecology	Full/ associate professor
	René	Kleijn	TUD		
	Mike	Buxton	TUD	Civil Engineering and Geosciences	Full/ associate professor
	Jelle	Joustra	TUD	Industrial Design Engineering	Postdoc
	József	Faitli	UM	Earth Sciences and Engineering	Professor
	Ábel Dániel	Antonovits	UM	Earth Sciences and Engineering	Assistant Research Fellow
	Emese	Sebe	UM	Materials and Chemical Engineering	PhD student
	Gábor	Gyarmati	UM	Faculty of Materials and Chemical Engineering	PhD student
	Andrea	Simon	UM	Faculty of Materials and Chemical Engineering	Associate prof.
	Emese	Mesterné Kurovics	UM	Faculty of Materials and Chemical Engineering	assistant research fellow
	Alexandra	Hamza	UM	Faculty of Materials and Chemical Engineering	Departmental engineer
	András	Hegedűs	UM	Earth Sciences and Engineering	Associate professor
	Andrea	Simon	UM	Materials Sciences	Associate prof.
	Gábor	Mucsi	UM	Earth Sciences and Engineering	Professor
	Antti	Häkkinen	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Full/ associate professor
	Sami	Virolainen	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Director, Full/ associate professor
	Laura	Albareda	LUT	LBM	Full/ associate professor
	Miia	John	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Postdoc
	Minttu	Laukkanen	LUT	LBM	Postdoc
	Katja	Lahikainen	LUT	LENS / Industrial eng. & man.	Director, Postdoc
	Teemu	Kinnarinen	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Full/ associate professor
	Manivannan	Sethurajan	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Postdoc
	Svetlana	Butylina	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Postdoc
	Youssef	El Ouardi	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Postdoc
	Jan-Henk	Weblink	TUD	Mechanical, Maritime and Materials Engineering	Project manager

2

Topic	First name	Last name	Organisation	Faculty	Title
Research subtopic #2: Processing technologies in waste recycling	Yongxiang	Yang	TUD	Mechanical, Maritime and Materials Engineering	Full/ associate professor
	Alexander	Wandl	TUD		
	Sándor	Nagy	UM	Earth Sciences and Engineering	associate professor
	Máté	Petrik	UM	Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	assistant professor
	Gábor	Szepesi	UM	Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	associate professor
	Csaba	Póliska	UM	Materials and Chemical Engineering	associate professor
	Ákos	Cservenák	UM	Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	Senior lecturer
	Ferenc	Móricz	UM	Earth Sciences and Engineering	senior lecturer
	Viktoria	Mannheim	UM	Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	senior research associate
	Mária	Nagy Gáborné Ambrus	UM	Earth Sciences and Engineering	PhD student / associate research fellow
	Zsófia	Forgács	UM	Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	assistant lecturer
	Tuomas	Koiranen	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Full/ associate professor
	Harri	Nieminen	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Postdoc
	Mika	Horttanainen	LUT	LES/ Sustainable solutions	Full/ associate professor
	Aki	Mikkola	LUT	LES/Mechanical engineering	Full/ associate professor
Research subtopic #3: Circular manufacturing	David	Peck	TUD	Architecture and the Built Environment	Full/ associate professor
	Nina	Boorsma	TUD	Architecture and the Built Environment	Postdoc
	Jeremy	Faludi	TUD	Industrial Design Engineering	Full/ associate professor
	Benjamin	Sprecher	TUD	Industrial Design Engineering	Full/ associate professor
	Tillmann	Klein	TUD	Architecture and the Built Environment	Full/ associate professor
	Ingrid	de Pauw	TUD	Industrial Design Engineering	Lecturer
	Sagar	Dangal	TUD	Industrial Design Engineering	PhD
	Julieta	Bolaños Arriola	TUD	Industrial Design Engineering	PhD
	Sonja	van Dam	TUD	Industrial Design Engineering	Full/ associate professor
	Renske	van den Berge	TUD	Industrial Design Engineering	PhD
	Agnes	Takacs	UM	Faculty of Mechanical engineering and Informatics	associate professor

Topic	First name	Last name	Organisation	Faculty	Title
	Eszter	Borsodi	UM	Faculty of Mechanical engineering and Informatics	PhD student
	Géza	Németh	UM	Faculty of Mechanical engineering and Informatics	lecturer
	Zoltán	Musinszki	UM	Faculty of Economics	Associate Professor, Vice-Dean
	Klara	Szucsne Markovics	UM	Faculty of Economics	Associate Professor
	Ferenc	Sarka	UM	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	associate professor
	Zsolt	Tóbis	UM	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	master instructor
	Zoltán	Bihari	UM	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	associate professor
	Voith	Katalin	UM	Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	sen. research fellow
	János	Juhász	UM	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	Assistant Lecturer
	László	Erdei	UM	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	PhD Student
	Róbert	Skapinyecz	UM	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	associate professor
	Henriett	Matyi	UM	Logistics Engineering	PhD student
	Ákos	Cservenák	UM	Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	Senior lecturer
	Tamás	Bányai	UM	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	Full professor
	Csaba	Felho	UM	Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	associate professor
	Viktor	Molnar	UM	Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	associate professor
	Istvan	Sztankovics	UM	Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	senior lecturer
	László	Rónai	UM	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	senior lecturer
	József	Lénárt	UM	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	assistant lecturer
	György	Hegedűs	UM	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics	Full/ associate professor
	Ferenc	Madai	UM	Earth and Environmental Science and Engineering	Full / associate professor

Topic	First name	Last name	Organisation	Faculty	Title
	Eveliina	Repo	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Full/ associate professor
	Ekaterina	Laakso	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Full/ associate professor
	John	Bediako	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Researcher
	Emile	Massima Mouele	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Researcher
	Jutta	Nuortila-Jokinen	LUT	LENS / Separation sci.	Full/ associate professor
	Kaisa	Grönman	LUT	LES/ Sustainable solutions	Postdoc
Research subtopic #4: Sustainable energy transition - just transition	Behnam	Taebi	TUD	Technology, Policy and Management	
	Andy	van den Dobbelsteen	TUD	Architecture and the Built Environment	Full/ associate professor
	Cornelis	van de Kamp	TUD	Technology, Policy and Management	Acquisition manager
	Jaco	Quist	TUD	Technology, Policy and Management	Assistant professor
	Mahshid	Hasankhani	TUD	Industrial Design Engineering	PhD
	Deirdre	van Gameren	TUD	Architecture and the Built Environment	Project manager
	Nynke	van Uffelen	TUD	Technology, Policy and Management	PhD
	Tekla	Szép	UM	Faculty of Economics	associate professor
	Mohammad	Jaber	UM	Faculty of Economics	PhD Candidate
	Milán	Szőri	UM	Faculty of Materials and Chemical Engineering	full professor
	Katalin	Lipták	UM	Faculty of Economics	associate professor, head of department, vice-dean
	Ágnes	Horváth	UM	Faculty of Economics	associate professor
	Zsolt	Dobó	UM	Faculty of Materials and Chemical Engineering	Senior research fellow
	Hegedüs	Balázs	UM	Institute of Energy and Quality	PhD student
	Adrienn	Takácsné Papp	UM	Faculty of Economics	assistant lecturer
	Beáta	Siskáné-Szilasi	UM	Faculty of Earth Science and Engineering	associate professor
	Helga	Kovács	UM	Institute of Energy and Quality Affairs	head of the institute
	Marianna	Vadászi	UM	Faculty of Earth Science and Engineering	associate professor
	István	Szunyog	UM	Faculty of Earth Science and Engineering	associate professor
	Dóra	Szendi	UM	Faculty of Economics	associate professor
Zoltán	Nagy	UM	Faculty of Economics	associate professor	

Topic	First name	Last name	Organisation	Faculty	Title
	Matti	Kojo	LUT	LENS/ Social sci.	Full/ associate professor
	Jaana	Laine	LUT	LENS/ Social sci.	Lecturer
	Jouni	Havukainen	LUT	LES/ Sustainable solutions	Full/ associate professor

8.3. Annex 3 – Profile tables of researchers involved in CiRCLETECH hub activity from UNIM

Data	
Name	László Erdei
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	I am a PhD student and Category D
	I would like to defend my doctoral dissertation as soon as possible so that I can start my teaching/research career as an assistant professor at the University of Miskolc.
Link to profile	LINK
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	I have several years of research experience in the field of Circular Economy, as evidenced by several completed and qualified projects. My diploma thesis is also on CE. Its topic is related to Subtopic 3 i.e., research on inverse logistic processes in manufacturing that contribute to sustainable manufacturing. I plan to make an active contribution to the project through international mobility activities in the field of supply chain research. Specifically related to the levels of material and information flows within a manufacturing company. The aim is to maximise the return of reusable raw materials into the material cycle. I would like to document this delivery by simulation case studies.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short mobility • Teaching and knowledge exchange
Personnel motivation	Identify opportunities for international cooperation. Implement knowledge and best practices from other nations. To identify and connect high-quality researchers and their work in the field.

Data	
Name	Csilla Margit, CSISZÁR
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Associate professor / Category B
	I would like to habilitate.
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10027077&view=simple
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	Subtopic 3 - Circular manufacturing Research topic: Digital transformation, digital tools, digital skills, data protection, data security
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least two more articles in Scopus-indexed journals • 20% citation growth during the project implementation (3 years) • At least 1 Q1 publication
Personnel motivation	I hope to make substantial advancements in my scientific career. Recently, I've been investigating digitalization-related themes and have begun to investigate which factors impede and which promote digitalization's advancement, as well as which digital technologies and skills should be prioritised in the future. In these areas, I would appreciate the opportunity to collaborate with others and conduct joint research.

Data	
Name	Dr. Róbert Skapinyecz
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	associate professor / Category B
	As currently working as an associate professor, by the end of the project I would like to get closer in my career to passing the habilitation.
Link to profile	https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Robert-Skapinyecz , https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=authors10029559
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	I earned my university degree in transportation engineering. My research carrier till now has been focused mostly on the analysis and optimization of various logistics systems (my PhD thesis focused on the risk assessment of logistics networks). During my research, I also occasionally came in contact with the area of reverse logistics and I previously authored a few papers related to that topic as well. Under today's circumstances, I think that this area became an extremely vital part of sustainable development and I would be interested to explore the logistics aspects of circular manufacturing (Subtopic 3) in this context. As a transportation engineer, I'm also very interested in the development of electromobility, for which the topic of circular manufacturing in the context of battery production and recycling also became a central question.
Personal scientific objective	Linking to existing research teams and having at least one or two new co-authors. At least two more articles in Scopus-indexed journals.
Personnel motivation	Part of my motivation for participating in the research project is that I consider this area vitally important in achieving the goals of sustainability and carbon neutrality. From a personal perspective, I think that on the one hand, it would be a privilege for me to contribute to this research from the side of logistics, but I think that it would also open up new possibilities for me in terms of scientific visibility and longer term cooperation with other researchers. In terms of research ideas, I would like to more deeply explore the opportunities for efficiency gains lying in the optimization of reverse logistics systems connected to circular manufacturing, but I'm also open to other research avenues as well.

Data	
Name	Emese Sebe
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	PhD student/Category D
	I started my PhD studies in 2019 and I would like to get the doctoral degree during the time of this project.
Link to profile	Sebe Emese (Energiagazdálkodás) (MTMT)
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	I have a bachelor's degree in environmental engineering. I specialized in waste management. I was experimenting with a sunflower seed hull as a biosorbent to remove heavy metals from solutions. During my master's I was studying materials engineering specialising in energy and quality. My PhD research is focusing on the energy recovery of municipal solid waste by pyrolysis and gasification. Since the beginning of my BSc studies, I am related to waste management, so I think I will be able to help with the work of the waste mining research group.
Personal scientific objective	I would like to publish at least one paper in a high-ranking journal with international co-authors. I would like to be cited for the first time by papers published in journals with IF.
Personnel motivation	Firstly, I would like to finish my PhD studies and after that, I would like to be a valuable member of the scientific community at the University of Miskolc. I think this project is a great opportunity, especially now, at the beginning of my scientific career to get new international professional relationships. By getting to know other professionals in the field I can get many different points of view and probably many new ideas and directions. Lately, I was investigating the possibility of turning MSW into an adsorbent. I am interested in this topic, so if there is someone in this project with a similar research topic, hopefully, we can talk about it one day.

Data	
Name	Milán Szőri
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Category A (Full professor, group leader, project manager)
	Full professor, group leader, project manager
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=authors10026087 https://orcid.org/my-orcid?orcid=0000-0003-4895-0999 https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=8522212800 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Milan-Szori https://scholar.google.hu/citations?user=X-24OaEAAAAJ&hl=hu https://www.linkedin.com/in/mil%C3%A1n-sz%C5%91ri-27840b51/
Role in the research group	Researcher, group leader, project manager
Background	I have extensive computational chemistry background in understanding oxidation and thermal decomposition mechanisms of some molecules produced from biomass. I also studied elementary reactions having atmospheric relevance.
Personal scientific objective	Based on my experiences in the computation of the energy-content of different chemicals, several reactions relevant to the chemical industry and atmospheric processes can be evaluated according to their energy consumption. Less energy-intensive procedures can be suggested using computational evidence.
Personal motivation	I would like to combine my expertise and specialities with those of collaborators to create new added value which can be disseminated as publications. Furthermore, I would inspire others with the beauty of computational chemistry, and I would like to learn new technologies and establish new long-term collaborations.

Data	
Name	Zsófia Forgács
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	assistant lecturer / Category D
	At the end of the project, after defending my doctoral thesis, I would like to work as an assistant professor. I aim to move from category D to C.
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10054567
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	<p>I graduated in electrical engineering with a specialization in industrial automation. In recent years, I have participated in various control technology R&D projects, where my tasks were mostly related to PLC, SCADA and HMI systems, and the development of measurement and data acquisition systems. My doctoral research topic is related to image processing for industrial purposes.</p> <p>Within this project, I chose the Processing technologies in the waste recycling subtopic (Subtopic 2), because previously, I was involved in the development of the control system of an RDF gasifier. I would like to learn more about waste processing technologies and actively participate in solving related problems in the future.</p>
Personal scientific objective	I would like to link to existing research teams and to have at least one or two new co-authors. Also, I aim to write at least two articles in Scopus-indexed journals.
Personnel motivation	I would like to advance my publication record. I don't have much experience in publishing in international journals, so I would like to aim for this together with the new collaborators acquired during the project. My interest in waste recycling grew during the development of the control system of the RDF gasifier. I hope that by learning about modern waste processing technologies, I can contribute to the further development of the existing gasification technology at the University; or participate as a researcher in further related R&D projects.

Data	
Name	Gábor Gyarmati
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	PhD student
	Desired career stage at the end of the project: I would like to defend my PhD thesis and become a research fellow.
Link to profile	https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Gabor-Gyarmati https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7568-6922 https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10067192 https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=57210949775
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	BSc Materials Engineer and MSc Metallurgical Engineer, doing research on the treatment and purification of liquid aluminium alloys for 6 years (since the 2 nd year of BSc course). Received the Excellent Young Foundryman Award from the Association of Hungarian Foundries and the Nematik Award by Nematik Győr Kft. Liquid metal treatment, the reduction of oxide content and the microstructural control of intermetallics are especially important for manufacturing high-quality products from recycled aluminium waste. Recycling aluminium is connected to Subtopic 1 - Processing technologies in waste recycling.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least two more articles in Scopus-indexed journals; • 20% citation growth during the project implementation (3 years), • Linking to existing research teams and having at least one or two new co-authors.
Personnel motivation	I am interested in all aspects of the metallurgy and processing technologies of light alloys, as well as the characterization of other related materials. I would like to deepen my knowledge in the area of aluminium recycling, and I am planning to do research that is focused on the characterization of the quality of recycled aluminium alloy ingots and products manufactured from recycled material. I am open to collaborations and looking forward to meeting new partners and advancing in recycling-related topics through conducting collaborative research.

Data	
Name	Alexandra Hamza
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Category D
	Obtaining a PhD
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10074415&view=pubTable
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	For nearly 6 years, I have been involved in research related to various ceramic materials, mainly clays and concretes. Regarding the topic of clays, I participated in several research projects, the focus of which I investigated the use of various industrial wastes in the brick and tile industry, for example, red mud, and metallurgical slag. In addition, I also investigated the use of lignite-fired power plant fly ash in cement foams. My previous works also touched on the topic of foam glass, in which we dealt with the recycling of CRT glass. In the course of my work, I have in mind the replacement of primary materials used in the ceramics industry with recycled materials. In addition, I would like to use the properties of certain industrial wastes to improve shape ability by using clay as a plasticizing additive as a member of the team "Processing technologies in waste recycling".
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least two more articles (including Q1 or D1) in Scopus-indexed journals • Citation growth during the project implementation (3 years) • First International conference presentation • Improve English vocabulary and speaking skills
Personnel motivation	Joining the project allows me to further develop my current professional and English language skills. In addition, I consider cooperation with other universities to be useful, as this way we can more easily provide assistance and exchange experiences with researchers working in the same subject area. At the same time, teamwork is usually more effective and gives individuals stronger motivation than working alone.

Data	
Name	József Lénárt
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Assistant lecturer / Category D
	Category C
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10026162
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	I started my PhD research in 2007, my research field is mechatronics, with particular attention to the areas of industrial robotics, control and measurement technology, embedded systems, machine vision and digital image processing, sensor technology, and PLC programming. I am employed at the University of Miskolc, Department of Machine Tools and Mechatronics as an assistant lecturer. My subtopic is the 3 rd : Circular manufacturing, because sensor technology, measurements and industrial robotics are part of the area.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20% citation growth during the project implementation (3 years); • At least two more articles in Scopus-indexed journals;
Personnel motivation	My main motivation is to improve my publishing performance and I would like to advance one degree in my career. On the other hand, the motivation is to increase my citation number. I would like to get to know the strategies, methods, and techniques of researchers at foreign universities, in connection with how they publish in prestigious journals.

Data	
Name	Ferenc Móricz
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	senior lecturer
	Within a year I would like to move from the level of senior lecturer to associate professor.
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=authors10045632 https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6708-3507
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	My researching area is mainly mineralogy, and geochemistry, as well as the different types of instrumental material analysis. I have 10 years of experience measuring with wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectroscope (WDXRF) Subtopic 2 - Processing technologies in waste recycling
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linking to existing research teams and having at least one or two new co-authors. • At least two more articles in Scopus-indexed journals; • - A Q1 publication (I would be the main author.)
Personnel motivation	It would be good to share information with those scientists, who work in the same researching area. It would also be good to exchange experience with the professionals who also make WDXRF measurements.

Data	
Name	Orsolya Kovács
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	departmental engineer
	I would like to confirm my position and grow professionally to make good progress.
Link to profile	-
Role in the research group	researcher
Background	<p>I worked for years in the laboratory of a foam glass thermal insulation manufacturing company as a research assistant (chemical technician). We made thermal insulating foam glass granules from waste glasses. In this way, we gave a new life to the glass that would have ended up as waste. The product is also used as lightweight fillings on walkable and green roofs. They are also placed under sports grounds and there are many special fields of using the foam glass products.</p> <p>I worked in a school as a laboratory assistant during my university studies. I wrote my thesis on the topic of polymer (PEEK) spinal implants. I moved to Miskolc last year and since then I have been working in the Polymer Technology Laboratory at the university as a departmental engineer.</p> <p>My first degree is in teaching and I also have experience as a journalist.</p>
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jointing with existing research teams and writing at least one or two publications. • Creation of informative, promotional and educational articles, and documents on the Circletech topic.
Personnel motivation	Biomaterials, especially high-performance plastics, are expensive in terms of their raw materials and production technology. I would be happy to participate in the research of an economical, zero-waste or cradle-to-cradle technology.

Data	
Name	Prof. Dr. Habil György Czél
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Full professor
	Obtaining DSc title Further development of the Polymer Technology research group on Biomaterials at MU
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=authors10012947
Role in the research group	Lead Researcher
Background	In the field of space materials, I touched the High-Tech sphere as a Young engineer, then I dealt with metallic materials technology development and the development of bio-ceramics. For the last 20 years have been doing research in the field of biomaterials and bio-implants. My research career so far has been based on the replacement of synthetic polymers with natural biopolymers and recycled synthetic polymers. My research area is related to the topics of Subtopic 3 - Circular manufacturing. The research task focuses primarily on the research of synthetically produced but naturally degradable polymer hybrid composites. Self-degradable bio-composite irrigation tube development is my recent research topic. Missing the manufacturing technology of it. As a doctor father develops the production and application technology of new types of hybrid composites. With the cooperation of the regional bio-implant industry (Mediox Ltd.), we are working on technology changes in the development of polymer cages for human spinal surgery.
Personal scientific objective	2 pcs. EU or minimum Hungarian patent application 2 pcs. International conference presentation, At least two more articles in Scopus-indexed journals;10% citation growth during the project implementation, D1 publications
Personnel motivation	In Hungary 440 plastic processing companies produce polymeric products. They would like to improve their products in the direction of green or bio polymers. The balance between biopolymers and synthetic polymers does not exist. The research base of biopolymers also does not exist at MU. During the covid period, I developed the Polymer Technology Laboratory with research equipment and a research group. The capacity of this laboratory is about 15 researchers today, but only 3 researchers + 1 PhD student + 2 MSc students carry out their activities in this laboratory. Missing the young researcher group generation next to me. The material development topic of biomaterials is perhaps more important than anything else today.

Data	
Name	György Hegedűs, PhD
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	associate professor, head of the institute
	I currently work as a university associate professor. I would like to increase the number of publications and citations required for the habilitation with the help of the application.
Link to profile	MTMT:10026571 Researchgate: Gyoergy-Hegedus orcid: 0000-0002-0081-8019
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	My research topics are related to CAD modelling, numerical methods of tool geometry generation and manufacturing processes. I am the head of the Institute of Machine Tools and Mechatronics and Institutional Department of Machine Tools since 2022 at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics. Due to the previously mentioned research topics the selected research subtopic is: Subtopic 3 - Circular manufacturing because the sensors, and industrial robotics, in my opinion, can be part of the area.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least two more articles in Scopus-indexed journals; • Increasing the number of Q1-Q2 published articles; • Obtaining the habilitation;
Personnel motivation	My main motivation is to improve publishing performance and I am curious about all topics related to the field of machine tools, manufacturing, CAD modelling and related applications. On the other hand, the motivation is to increase my Scopus/WoS citation numbers. I would like to get to know the strategies, methods, and techniques of researchers at foreign universities, in connection with how they publish in prestigious journals.

Data	
Name	Géza Németh
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	professor assistant/ Category C
	I want to fulfil my doctoral thesis in the area of self-help mechanisms, partly decreasing the energy-consumption with this principle and assuring the dismantlability and reusing of the mechanisms after changing the worn parts on the other hand.
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/api/publication?format=html&labelLang=hun&sort=publishedYear_desc&cond=authors;eq:10028626
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	Subtopic 3 - Circular manufacturing Efficiency and the life rating are essential characteristics of mechanical drives. The traction drives with proper geometry can avoid the geometrical slip and their efficiency can exceed that of the gear drives. The elements have hardened steel surfaces, the lubricant is rheopectic. There is no danger in thinning the oil film and consequently in connecting the asperities. The traction drives are relatively noiseless, they are applicable for increasing speed. There are some problems to be solved in friction drive. This is the necessity of clamping force. A simple machine element usually makes a constant clamping force, and a tensioning mechanism can be too complicated. The ideal solution is a simple design which assures a clamping force that is proportional to the instantaneous external load requirements. I suggest a modified machine element – a helical torsion spring, an elastic one, instead of the original, rigid annular wheel – that comprises both the driving and clamping functions, and the latter one is proportional to the external load so that the principle of self-help operates.
Personal scientific objective	Linking to existing research teams and having at least one or two new co-authors. At least one more article in Scopus-indexed journals;
Personal motivation	I have had an idea for years to develop a simple usable drive with speed reduction. To prove the principle of operation requires partly high research work on the field of strength of materials and partly to manufacture the special elements of the drive and at last control the proper operability on a test rig. I have made some analytical stress calculations but I have no experience in numeric methods. I hope the topic is interesting enough to find a partner in this area.

Data	
Name	Ákos Cservenák
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	senior lecturer, PhD, Category C
	I would like to become an associate professor in 2 years and prepare for the habilitation in 4 years.
Link to profile	http://geik.uni-miskolc.hu/intezetek/LOG/staff.en.php?id=339 https://www.linkedin.com/in/akos-cservenak-57008584/ https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=57195609646 https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8439-5737 https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10052869
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	6 years of research and education experiments on mechatronics and later logistics. Formerly I dealt with different mechatronic systems, such as industrial robots and AGVs. Later I had the possibility to the Institute of Logistics. Here I got acquainted with different logistics systems. One of my research activities dealt with two different SmartBins. The smaller one was transformed from a normal small wastebin into an automated opening, and feedback-giving one. The other type can be found near flat houses. This bin has several sensors to locate the flatness of the waste. My PhD research was carried out on an AGV, and its movement method was developed, it was successfully defended last year. Other smaller research activities connected to Industry 4.0 technologies, simulations, vehicles, traffic systems, and drones.
Personal scientific objective	My recent research topics are related to Logistics, mechatronics, Industry 4.0 technologies, robotics, industrial robots, mobile robots, automated material handling equipment, different simulations, vehicles, traffic systems, smart trash bins, and drones. I would like to get acquainted with new techniques, new methods, and good practices, then extend my research to the international level and use it in education. As mentioned above, I would like to make the habilitation, to perform some of the criteria I would like to publish at least two Q1-2 papers, more Scopus-indexed papers and supervise a PhD student. Furthermore, to extend my connection network I would like to join different researcher groups. Finally, I would like to get acquainted with new techniques, new methods, and good practices, then extend my research to the international level and use it in education.
Personnel motivation	<p>Regarding my scientific career, firstly I would like to become an associate professor, and later make the habilitation and become a full professor.</p> <p>Regarding research topics, I would like to examine the AGV/AMR systems, the different Industry 4.0 technologies, and their use in logistics systems. Furthermore, I would like to deal with smart trash bin systems, different simulation techniques and also automated material handlings equipment, such as industrial robots, or drones. I think these topics are up-to-date, and I like to deal with these topics and know new people, who also deal with these research fields.</p> <p>With international co-authors from partner universities, I would like to write at least two Q1-2 ranked papers.</p>

Data	
Name	Dr. Sarka, Ferenc
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	associate professor
	My goal is to improve the quality of publication activity in the Q category (from Q4 to Q3-Q2). Publishing a publication with an impact factor
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=authors10025934 https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=57195971838 https://orcid.org/my-orcid?orcid=0000-0003-3136-4248
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	During my research work so far, 3D technologies (CAD, FEM, Scan, Print) played the main role. Whether it is joint research with students or research and machine design tasks for industrial partners. During the projects, the finite element simulations were my favourite. I am currently working on the simulation of testing bolted joints. This topic may be relevant in circular manufacturing. This year, I started studying digitization technologies in a little more detail, in connection with an industrial inquiry.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First publication with impact factor. • Reach 10 publications in Scopus
Personnel motivation	Why should I join this project? I would like to learn how research work is done in other countries. It would be nice to see an insight into the techniques and technologies that the partner universities are bringing to the forefront of the world. If I can learn just a small part of the research culture, it will still be a step forward for me compared to the current state. The harmful effects of global climate change are already here with us today, if as a result of our research, we can do even a little to reverse this, then that would be a very big result for the project..

Data	
Name	Andrea Simon
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Category B
	Habilitation
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10015093&view=pubTable https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1498-7697
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	Nearly 20 years of experience in research and education related to materials sciences and technologies, with a special focus on the glass and ceramic materials. At the beginning of my research carrier, I worked on aluminium matrix composites reinforced with ceramic particles. Then my research activity turned towards ceramics and silicates, including glasses and glazes, focusing on the microstructure, and the physical and mechanical properties. Recently, due to industrial needs, we started to investigate the recycling issues and possibilities of several waste material streams (originating from households or the industry). Nowadays, I work with my PhD students on the recyclability of industrial wastes as a secondary raw material for foam glasses as a member of the team "Processing technologies in waste recycling".
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linking to existing research teams and having at least one or two new co-authors. • At least two more articles (including Q1 or D1) in Scopus-indexed journals. • Citation growth during the project implementation (3 years) • Receiving an individual research grant.
Personnel motivation	One of the strongest motivations to join this project was to increase my career stage by using the possibilities given in the research teams, e.g. the international research activities. As I experienced in my earlier projects, collaboration with international teams always results in a higher level of research work and publication activity. Furthermore, the other universities have equipment which can be used in our research area to gain a more detailed view.

Data	
Name	Zsolt Tóbis
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Master Instructor
	Strengthening publication activity in Scopus
Link profile	to https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=authors10026106 https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=57219990966&origin=recordPage https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4711-2224
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	During my research work so far, 3D technologies (CAD, CAM) and acoustic measurements have played a major role. Whether it is joint research with students or research and machine design tasks of industrial partners. Acoustic tests are very important for almost all products to comply with environmental protection and workplace safety regulations. During my work, I experienced that in many cases the correct use of 3D technologies requires a lot of learning and experience. Therefore, I would like to carry out research work in the two subject areas mentioned above, but mostly in the field of 3D technologies, connected to sub-topic 3.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reach 6 publications in Scopus • Increase the quality of publications to Q3
Personnel motivation	I would like to expand my knowledge in the field of 3D technologies, for which this project seems to be a good opportunity. 3D technologies are the design and production technologies of the future, so knowing them is unavoidable. Nowadays, environmental protection and sustainable economic activities play a very important role, so I would like to further develop my knowledge in connection with this. It is very attractive to do all this in an international community.

Data	
Name	Mária Nagy Gáborné Ambrus
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	PhD student, associate research fellow / Category D
	By the end of the project, I would like to finish my PhD studies and defend my thesis. After obtaining the PhD degree, I would also like to improve my career stage.
Link to profile	https://orcid.org/my-orcid?orcid=0000-0002-7171-6642 https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10065416
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	My master's and PhD studies were related to solid waste processing and recycling technologies, mainly industrial and mining wastes such as fly ash, red mud, and mining gangue but also including communal waste processing possibilities and technologies. As a researcher, I participated in various research projects related to different industrial waste recycling and WEEE processing (e.g. LED, LCD wastes, airbag utilisation from EoLVs). I worked on the application and optimisation of processing technologies, high-value-added product preparation possibilities and a combination of waste streams for synergetic utilisation.
Personal scientific objective	During the project, I would like to join the existing research team(s) and have at least one or two new co-authors for further publication and research options. Furthermore, I am planning the publication of articles in Scopus-indexed journals (possibly Q1 publication as well).
Personnel motivation	Regarding my PhD studies, I believe that having researchers from other institutes with different research equipment should prove to be beneficial for the continuation of my thesis. An outsider's perspective and the possibility of carrying out new and different experiments would be valuable. Considering the existing experimental data, finding other scientists working in the field of sampling and homogenization of pastes with more experience would provide great assistance with the development and optimization of my current research results.

Data	
Name	Dr. Csaba Felhő
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	director in the institute, associate professor / Category B
	Achieving habilitation
Link to profile	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0997-666X , https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=54894390600 , https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10014000&view=simpleList
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	In the area of circular manufacturing, I have mainly dealt with increasing the efficiency of various cutting processes. Within this, I mainly dealt with the simulation of cutting processes with single and multi-point tools, and with the examination and pre-estimation of the roughness of the machined surfaces.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linking to existing research teams and having at least one or two new co-authors. • Receiving an individual research grant (OTKA, MSCA, etc.) • 20% citation growth during the project implementation (3 years)
Personnel motivation	My primary motivation is to gain professional and human relations at the participating leading universities, which will enable us to jointly prepare prestigious applications and publications in the future. From a professional point of view, in the context of circular manufacturing, it would be important to investigate how it is possible to reuse worn-out machine parts with the least possible expenditure of energy and money, as this would also help reduce the environmental burden.

Data	
Name	Henriett Matyi
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Category D – First-stage researcher, PhD student
	My current goal is to get my PhD and I would like to become a university teaching assistant. After my PhD, I would like to become a senior lecturer.
Link to profile	MTMT: 10079354
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	<p>Subtopic 3: Circular manufacturing</p> <p>My research area within logistics is packaging, and unit load training. I have conducted several literature reviews on the topic, with a special focus on sustainable packaging. Nowadays, more and more companies are striving for environmentally conscious manufacturing and packaging. In my research, the aim is to develop a system that uses digitalization to select the right packaging for a new product. An important part of manufacturing is packaging, forming unit loads, which will only be part of a closed economy if recycling is achieved.</p>
Personal scientific objective	Link to existing research groups and have at least one or two new co-authors. Q1 publication
Personnel motivation	<p>Moving forward as a researcher: as a PhD student, I am very happy to have had the opportunity to participate in this project. My main personal goal is to expand my research experience.</p> <p>Research topic: As far as the research topic is concerned, I would welcome the opportunity to share our scientific research with other researchers working in a similar field, and we could write a paper together, thus developing our mutual knowledge and understanding. We would like to share a joint research paper with other researchers.</p>

Data	
Name	János Juhász
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Assistant Lecturer / Category D
	I would like to finish my dissertation and defend the PhD. to become an Assistant professor in 2023.
Link to profile	MTMT id.: 10061051 https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10061051&view=simpleList
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	Development of design methods for just-in-sequence supply. Subtopic 3 - Circular manufacturing The development of just-in-sequence supply chain planning methods is a priority research area in the manufacturing and service industries: to organize companies' traditional and complex processes efficiently and economically; to operate them is essential to serve intermodal logistics activities and to manage tasks.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short summer/autumn mobility • Teaching and knowledge exchange
Personnel motivation	I would like to develop my international research opportunities, build cooperative relationships with international universities, and learn about joint research opportunities in the field of corporate manufacturing logistics processes.

Data	
Name	János Juhász
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Assistant Lecturer / Category D
	I would like to finish my dissertation and defend the PhD. to become an Assistant professor in 2023.
Link to profile	MTMT id.: 10061051 https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10061051&view=simpleList
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	Development of design methods for just-in-sequence supply. Subtopic 3 - Circular manufacturing The development of just-in-sequence supply chain planning methods is a priority research area in the manufacturing and service industries: to organize companies' traditional and complex processes efficiently and economically; to operate them is essential to serve intermodal logistics activities and to manage tasks.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short summer/autumn mobility • Teaching and knowledge exchange
Personnel motivation	I would like to develop my international research opportunities, build cooperative relationships with international universities, and learn about joint research opportunities in the field of corporate manufacturing logistics processes.

Data	
Name	Klára SZŰCSNÉ MARKOVICS
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Category B – associate professor
	During the project, I would like to establish my research for habilitation. In addition, I would like to improve my professional skills and write publications of high quality.
Link to profile	https://vm.mtmt.hu/www/index.php?AuthorID=10027084 https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5842-6459 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Klara-Szucsne-Markovics https://scholar.google.hu/citations?user=GfcEOPAAAAAJ&hl=hu
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	<p>I defended my PhD thesis in 2014, whose topic was The process and methods of preparing investment decisions in the case of domestic manufacturing companies. (Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), 2014) Since 2010 I deal with capital budgeting methods. In addition to this topic, nowadays my research focuses on the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – the role of small and medium-sized enterprises in social innovation, – cost management in business practice, – applied methods of facility management.
Personal scientific objective	<p>Taking part in joint research is a good opportunity to publish scientific articles in high-quality journals (Scopus, WoS, Q1, Q2). Other goals are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – joining existing research teams and building relationships with new co-authors, – publishing at least two publications per year in high-quality journals, – increasing citation rate at least by 10% during the project implementation (3 years). <p>Joint research provides a good opportunity to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – develop international research networks; – exchange our knowledge and experience; – create an international research database.
Personnel motivation	<p>I would like to join an international research team and cooperate with some international researchers. I would be glad to become a useful member of an international research network and publish scientific articles in high-quality Journals with international co-authors. I would like to improve my professional skills and gain experience in international research. In addition, I would like to use the experiences of the common work, and the results of joint research for my habilitation.</p>

Data	
Name	Mohammad Jaber
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	PhD Candidate
	As a PhD candidate, the desired career stage at the end of the project would likely be that of a postdoctoral researcher or a junior faculty member.
Link to profile	Mohammad Jaber (0000-0001-8808-4170) (orcid.org) Mohammad Jaber (MTMT)
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	As a graduate student, I focused on investigating the intersections of energy poverty, climate change, and economic growth in the context of the sustainable energy transition. My research included analyzing data, conducting literature reviews, and presenting findings in academic journals and conferences.
Personal scientific objective	As a PhD candidate and a researcher, I am looking for more collaborations, publishing in high-quality journals, presenting at international conferences, and networking with other researchers.
Personnel motivation	<p>My primary motivation for participating in this research group is to contribute to the advancement of knowledge on sustainable energy transition in the European context. Specifically, I am interested in investigating the interplay between energy poverty, energy transition, poverty, and climate change, with a particular focus on the implementation of energy communities as a strategy to mitigate these issues. This scientific topic is of great importance to me as it addresses the pressing issues of energy poverty and pollution related to coal use in heating and cooking, which disproportionately affect marginalized communities in Europe.</p> <p>I have a long-standing hypothesis that I wish to develop, which posits that the implementation of energy communities can serve as a means to not only transition towards a more sustainable energy system but also to tackle energy poverty and pollution. I believe that by working in collaboration with other researchers in this field, I will be able to gain new insights and contribute to the body of knowledge on sustainable energy transition in Europe.</p>

Data	
Name	István Sztankovics, PhD
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	senior lecturer / Category B
	I aim to reach the associate professor position and improve my ranking within the category.
Link to profile	MTMT ID: 10025173 Scopus ID: 55619681100 ResearchGate: Istvan-Sztankovics ORCID: 0000-0002-1147-7475 Google Scholar ID: 83P1Q3oAAAAJ
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	In my career so far, I participated mainly in researching finish machining procedures, such as rotational turning, quick-point and in-feed grinding, hard turning, and high-feed milling. I defended my PhD thesis on the topic of rotational turning. I also studied assembly lines of transmissions. The aims of these research activities were the improvement of productivity, machined surface quality and lifetime of the product. This connects with "Subtopic 3 - Circular manufacturing" since the improvement of the quality of the machined parts leads to higher lifetime and therefore helps the waste reduction.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20% citation growth during the project implementation (3 years) • A Q1 publication
Personnel motivation	My motivations for participation in the work of the subtopic research group are to advance in my research career by the continuation of my study presented in my PhD thesis, which will be the basis of my habilitation in the future; and to work in research groups which help me improve my research skills in addition to have more partners with whom I can work together on my topic.

Data	
Name	Viktor Molnar, PhD
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Associate professor / Category B
	Professor, Category A
Link to profile	MTMT ID: 10024770
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	Past research activity incorporates the efficiency of machining procedures applied in the automotive industry based on indicators connected to the material removal process. This topic is connected to the circular economy by the analysis of the energy and material consumption during machining. The main foci are the main hard machining procedures: hard turning and grinding. Another topic is the analysis of the accuracy and surface quality of hard-machined parts. This research topic aims to the reparability and the increase of the life of common industrial parts such as gear wheels or bearing rings. The research results contribute to the circular economy through the development of durable and remanufactured components.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications in D1 journals (3 papers) and Q1 journals (6 papers) • Increase of citations: 10% per year. • Participation in international conferences (1 per year)
Personnel motivation	Reaching the career stage category A needs an increase of high-quality publications and cooperation with international researchers and publishing papers in co-authorship. The increased number of citations is also a requirement, which can be reached by this type of research and publication activity. The mentioned research topics should be extended by in-depth microeconomic analyses to validate the results by economic efficiency indicators.

Data	
Name	Agnes Takacs, PhD
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Associate professor
	I would like to improve the quality of my publication activity: IF papers, and more Scopus papers
Link to profile	MTMT ID: 10023068, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3210-6964, Scopus ID: 57195975325
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	During the period 2005-2010, I was dealing with my PhD research. I dealt with methodological design, focusing on the early stage of the design process: how to generate concepts for a given problem. Since then, I had not too much time to deal with this special field of science deeply, although I would have liked to. Instead, I spent time getting acquainted with the basic knowledge of environmentally friendly design. Now as the environment gets more attention, it would be useful to check the recent studies in the field of Circular manufacturing (Subtopic 3) in connection with design theories.
Personal scientific objective	Now I have a first-year PhD student. I aim to supervise her PhD work well and help her find foreign connections to her PhD work. The project could help us find a different point of view on design theories. I would like to increase the number of my Scopus-indexed papers from 4 to 10. A Q2 publication would be also great to absolve.
Personnel motivation	With my research, I turned to environmentally friendly design, because this is very important for me to leave a smaller ecological footprint. I also have a subject, Environmentally friendly design, and as a lecturer, I would like to give up-to-date knowledge to the students. This way I always improve the lecture notes, when I read a new publication on this topic. But it would be great to find new streams.

Data	
Name	Emese Mesterné Kurovics
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	assistant research fellow / Category C
	At the end of the project at least I would like to be a research fellow or an assistant professor.
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10063877&view=pubTable https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Emese-Kurovics
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	<p>I have received my PhD degree in 2022 from the University of Miskolc. During my PhD studies, I investigated the possibility of producing mullite ceramics with increased mechanical properties using relatively cheap raw materials. Now I work as an assistant research fellow at the Institute of Ceramics and Polymer Engineering.</p> <p>I have nearly five years of experience in research and education related to materials sciences and technologies, especially ceramic materials. Now I am ready to start a new research topic and interested in the theme of reducing the emission of greenhouse gases produced during the technology.</p>
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least two more articles (including Q1 or D1) in Scopus-indexed journals. • Linking to existing research teams and having at least one or two new co-authors. • Receiving an individual research grant.
Personnel motivation	<p>By joining this project, I would like to increase my career stage by using the possibilities given in the research teams.</p> <p>Collaboration with international teams always results in a higher level of research work and publication activity. Furthermore, the other universities may have equipment that can use in our research area to gain a more detailed view. I also would like to improve my English vocabulary and speaking skills.</p>

Data	
Name	Máté Petrik
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	assistant professor
	I am currently working as an assistant professor, and I would like to become an associate professor. Preparing habilitation thesis.
Link to profile	https://geik.uni-miskolc.hu/intezetek/EVG/staff.php?id=66 https://hu.linkedin.com/in/m%C3%A1t%C3%A9-petrik-4a1b86142 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0034-464X
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	I started my research career 6 years ago as a PhD student. I successfully defended my dissertation a year and a half ago. My research topic was the optimisation of heat exchanger systems. The studies cover both operational and performance issues, so waste recovery is part of my profile on several levels. In addition to heat exchanger structures, I also work on the optimization of steel structures. These steel structures are an integral part of any plant and have a significant impact on energy consumption both during construction and in normal operation.
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receiving an individual research grant (especially an OTKA project); • at least two more articles in Scopus-indexed journals; • one of these is a Q1 publication.
Personnel motivation	I want to join the project for several reasons. On the one hand, I want to develop professionally, become an associate professor, and habilitate. On the other hand, the project would allow me to get to know colleagues from foreign universities and write high-impact articles on possible joint work. During my PhD research, I mainly focused on shell-and-tube and finned-tube heat exchangers in chemical environments, but I would like to extend my research to other sectors.

Data	
Name	Hegedüs Balázs
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	PhD student; Category D
	By the end of the project, I wish to become an assistant professor / post-doctoral fellow.
Link to profile	MTMT https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10067641
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	For my PhD research, I am working on an alternative, sustainable way of plastic waste processing, pyrolysis. This method helps not only with waste disposal, but also able to create value-added materials such as liquid fuel. So far numerous information has been gathered regarding the behaviour of different plastics during pyrolysis and the composition of the products.
Personal scientific objective	By participating in the research group, I wish to further my research regarding plastic pyrolysis and discover new projects/methods connected to the sustainability of the energy sector. I also wish to attend at least one international conference where I can present my research, and I wish to publish my work in a Scopus-indexed journal.
Personal motivation	My motivation for this project is similar to my PhD research, which is finding solutions to further sustainability. In this regard my main goal is to produce a value-added product from a material which is widely considered to be a global problem, that is plastic waste. With plastic waste, the goal isn't only to deal with the accumulation, therefore, lessening the environmental impact, but also to alleviate the demand for fossil fuels. Achieving this is also my goal as a PhD student to further my career as a researcher.

Data	
Name	Ágnes HORVÁTH
Organisation	University of Miskolc (UM)
Position / Career stage	<p>Current position, job title / current career stage as defined in Frascati 2015 manual (available here): https://www.oecd.org/sti/frascati-manual-2015-9789264239012-en.htm</p> <p>Category B – associate professor</p>
	<p>Desired career stage at the end of the project - as defined in Frascati's 2015 manual and internal performance evaluation categories (UMIN)</p> <p>During the project, I would like to establish my research for habilitation, write publications of high quality and keep my current position.</p>
Link to profile	<p>https://vm.mtmt.hu/www/index.php?AuthorID=10022630 https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2043-5189 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Agnes_Kadar_Horvath</p>
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	<p>I wrote my PhD dissertation on the topic of factors influencing the price of district heating. (Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), 2011) Since 2008 I deal with the changes in the energy markets and the global energy challenges. My research focuses on the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Corporate energy management – Global energy challenges and strategic responses - Global energy crisis, liberalization of energy markets - Decarbonisation efforts in the energy sector - Energy efficiency in the industry - in particular with energy-intensive industries - District heating as a conscious tool of energy and environmental policy <p>I also dealt with the topic of the circular economy for a short time.</p>
Personal scientific objective	<p><i>The researcher's scientific objective:</i> Taking part in joint research is a good opportunity to publish scientific articles in high-quality Journals (Scopus, Q1, Q2).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Linking to existing research teams and having at least one or two new co-authors. - At least 1 more article in Scopus-indexed journals; - 10 % citation growth during the project implementation (3 years) <p><i>Connection to the overall objectives contribution to group objectives:</i> Research on efforts to increase energy efficiency and decarbonization in industry and the energy sector can contribute to the sustainable energy transition and the Circular Economy. An international database can be created and experiences can be exchanged through conducting joint research and collaboration.</p>
Personal motivation	<p>My main goal is to be able to increase the number of publications appearing in Scopus-indexed journals and the number of independent citations to my articles. I would like to use the experiences of the common work, and the results of my research for preparing for the habilitation. Within the framework of the project, I would like to establish my habilitation research topic. I would like to consciously build the research steps, from the finalization of the concept to the creation of an international database and the publication of high-quality journal articles. The main focus of my research is the strategic opportunities</p>

and responses of the energy sector and the energy-intensive industries to the grip of the global energy crisis and climate protection efforts.

Name	Katalin LIPTÁK PhD
Organisation	UM, the University of Miskolc, Faculty of Economics
Position / Career stage	associate professor (vice-dean, head of the department) Category B
	I am currently working as an associate professor and would like to move up by the end of the project period. Writing my habilitation thesis is an important goal.
Link to profile	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6714-0858 https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=57200544649 https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=authors10022096
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	<p>In my previous research, I looked at regional differences in the labour market in the Central and Eastern European areas. Today, the world of work is in a constant state of flux, with digitalisation, globalisation and the coronavirus epidemic making this phenomenon even more pronounced. Wage work in the classical sense is now understood in a different context, with the need to find individual solutions for members of disadvantaged communities. Local communities can do a lot in this respect. I looked at social innovation in small villages. I have found that local community solutions can often provide jobs for the unemployed, and even help to solve the problem of energy poverty if they work together.</p> <p>My focus has shifted towards sustainable and green labour markets and most recently, my colleagues have analysed the process of decarbonisation in selected firms in the European Union from a profitability perspective. The focus of our research is on energy companies operating coal-fired power plants in the EU as these companies are most seriously affected by the need to comply with the tightening requirements. Now I would like to join Subtopic 4 - Sustainable energy transition – Just transition.</p>
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linking to existing research teams and having at least one or two new co-authors. • Scopus-indexed journal (Q2 or Q3) publication.
Personal motivation	I believe that the analysis of the sustainable and green labour market is a topical and worthy area for research, as the need for live labour is decreasing due to robotisation and mechanisation, which further complicates the already low employment situation of people living in disadvantaged areas. The energy consumption of the inhabitants of disadvantaged settlements, energy poverty, is also a subject for study. The identification and case study-style presentation of good practices in municipalities could be useful.

Data	
Name	Adrienn Takácsné Papp
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Category D – researcher (without a PhD.)
	I'm currently working as an assistant lecturer, but I would like to defend my doctoral dissertation in a year and become an assistant professor, reaching Category C
Link to profile	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1443-5606 https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10071627
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	<p>Since 2017 I deal with energy challenges, energy transition and energy management at the global and local levels. My research focuses on the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - energy transition global and local level - energy management at the municipal level - energy policy - decarbonisation ways at an industry level - Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans - profitability and decarbonisation. <p>Most of my publications deal with the topics mentioned above, moreover, in 2020 and 2021 I was involved in two research groups on similar topics. I hope I could be a useful member of the team led by Tekla Szép (Sustainable Energy Transition - Just Transition; Sub-theme 4).</p>
Personal scientific objective	<p>Taking part in joint research is a good opportunity to publish scientific articles in high-quality journals (Scopus, Q1, Q2).</p> <p>I would like to be part of an international research team where I can transfer my knowledge of local and corporate energy management to a higher level. During the project, I would like to publish Q1, and/ or Scopus-indexed articles and increase my citations.</p>
Personal motivation	<p>My doctoral research topic is closely related to the focus of the project, so I hope that my results can support the common work, and the experience gained can increase the level of my research.</p> <p>I hope that during the three years of working together can build up a niche database. I hope I will be able to learn new methodologies and make new professional contacts that will be fruitful in the long term.</p>

Data	
Name	Dóra Szendi, PhD
Organisation	UMIN
Position / Career stage	<p>Current position, job title / current career stage as defined in Frascati 2015 manual (available here):</p> <p>Associate professor / Category B – Senior researcher: Researchers working in positions not as senior as top position but more senior than newly qualified doctoral graduates (IsCED level 8). Examples: ‘associate professor’ or ‘senior researcher’ or ‘principal investigator’.</p> <p>Desired career stage at the end of the project - as defined in Frascati's 2015 manual and internal performance evaluation categories (UMIN)</p> <p>I would like to maintain my position as an associate professor, of course with higher skills. I would like to prepare for the habilitation.</p>
Link to profile	<p>https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0010-9949</p> <p>linkedin.com/in/szendidora</p> <p>https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Dora-Szendi</p> <p>MTMT:</p> <p>https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=10037347</p>
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	Besides my main research field (convergence of peripheries in CEE), which has also a relationship to the project from the aspect of convergence processes, I was working on other projects before, which have dealt with smart cities and sustainable cities. First, in 2015 a project focused on smart local communities in a peripheral county of Hungary. Then from 2017 to 2022, I was a researcher in a project which mainly focused on smart cities and social innovation. Already analysed some segments of smart cities’ environmental components and the measurement models of smart cities. A little insight into the resilience of cities was also mentioned there. I have also a subject in the Master course titled Development of smart cities. These former researches could be linked to Subtopic 4 - Sustainable energy transition – Just transition.
Personal scientific objective	<p>Have better skills in the topic of smart sustainable cities, and working with other colleagues in teamwork. So, cooperative skills could be also developed further.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First PhD Supervision • At least two more articles in Scopus-indexed journals; • 20% citation growth during the project implementation (3 years) • A Q1 publication
Personal motivation	Through the research and results of the project work, I can get a broader insight into the field of sustainability, which is not so close to me based on previous research. So with the help of this research, I can provide some articles on this topic, which can contribute to increasing the number of “quality” publications and the citation scores further. Regarding the topic, the smart cities’ sustainability component is one of the most intensive applied/selected areas, and the performance measurement could be interesting to give forecasts for future processes. Besides that, resilience is a critical issue in nowadays rapidly changing conditions, so a broader analysis could be interesting from my side – whether smart cities are resilient or not.

Data	
Name	Marianna VADÁSZI (PhD)
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	Current position, job title / current career stage as defined in Frascati 2015 manual (available here): Associate Professor, Head of Department, Category B https://www.oecd.org/sti/frascati-manual-2015-9789264239012-en.htm
	Achieving reclassification from the Category B associate professor category to the highest grade/position Category A in which the research is usually conducted.
Link to profile	www.gas.uni-miskolc.hu , https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0649-311X , https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=authors10011285
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	<p>During the transition to a net zero emission EU energy system, hydrogen will play a significant role in combination with renewable electricity, using Europe's well-developed existing energy infrastructure. For hydrogen to fully develop, a tangible perspective must be created towards the development of a well-connected European hydrogen market over time.</p> <p>In the case of smaller capacities, hydrogen can be injected directly into the distribution network and the natural gas transmission system, and through it into underground gas storages.</p> <p>Therefore, from a network point of view, it is a key question where the hydrogen can enter the gas network since the source of hydrogen production probably does not coincide with the input of the pipe network.</p> <p>Subtopic 4. Sustainable energy transition</p>
Personal scientific objective	<p>Assessment of the relationship between domestic fossil energy carriers and the amount of hydrogen that can be produced, with the aim of independence from imports.</p> <p>To determine the amount of hydrogen that can be produced by using the various available technologies, especially highlighting the method of coal gasification. To determine the amount of non-emitted CO₂ with the examined technologies. Testing the effect of hydrogen after mixing it into the natural gas system.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20% citation growth during the project implementation (3 years) • A Q1 publication • Development of common educational material at a foreign partner university
Personal motivation	<p>To participate in the latest research directions, which are directly related to the circular economy and CO₂ emission reduction technologies. Development of the professional language, and involvement in training courses at partner universities. Acquisition of new competencies and their application in education.</p> <p>To green the energy systems, reduce import dependence and achieve the carbon-neutral goals of the European Union, it is essential to use domestic raw materials. I would like to examine the possibilities of reducing the carbon dioxide emissions of the Visonta power plant, which is built on the burning of lignite. Hydrogen will play a prominent role in the energy mix in the future, 96% of which is still produced from fossil energy sources. I would like to examine</p>

the role of lignite along the hydrogen value chain. I plan to develop educational material on the topic of hydrogen technologies, I would like to connect with other universities on the topic.

Data	
Name	László Rónai, PhD.
Organisation	University of Miskolc
Position / Career stage	senior lecturer / Category C
	I would like to keep my current career stage for the next three years.
Link to profile	https://m2.mtmt.hu/gui2/?type=authors&mode=browse&sel=authors10049561
Role in the research group	Researcher
Background	<p>I started my PhD studies in the field of mechatronics in 2016. My topic was related to industrial robots, its title was the development of the haptic feature of the robots to automate assembling processes. I defended my dissertation in 2020, and since then I have been employed by the university as a senior lecturer. I am the head of the Robert Bosch Department of Mechatronics since 2021 at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics. My research topics are modelling and simulation, industrial robotics, mechatronics, sensors, and PLC programming.</p> <p>I chose Subtopic 3 - Circular manufacturing because the sensors, and industrial robotics, in my opinion, can be part of the area.</p>
Personal scientific objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20% citation growth during the project implementation (3 years); • At least two more articles in Scopus-indexed journals;
Personnel motivation	My main motivation is to improve my publishing performance and I am curious about all topics related to the field of mechatronics, especially in the field of industrial robots. On the other hand, the motivation is to increase my citation number. I would like to get to know the strategies, methods, and techniques of researchers at foreign universities, in connection with how they publish in prestigious journals.

8.4. Annexe 4 – Processes

CiRCLETECH HUB Coordination processes initiation

Who: **WP2 leader**, Research Group leaders, Coordinator

When: Q1 2023

What:

- WP 2 leader initiates the process, inviting involved members
- The main communication channel and file-sharing platform is MS Teams **CiRCLETECH HUB Teams** group hosted by UNIM
- Defining the Research Group Vision, objectives SMART approach Including deliverables D2.2; D2.3; D2.4; D3.3; D4.3 and D4.4, defining review, monitoring and reporting in terms of methodology and time (frequency) and responsibilities – this is a guiding document

Research Group Coordination processes initiation

Who: **Research Group leaders**, Local Group Coordinators, Coordinator

When: Q1 2023

What:

- The Research Group leader initiates the process, inviting involved members
- The main communication channel and file-sharing platform is MS Teams **CiRCLETECH HUB Teams** group hosted by UNIM
- Inform participants about the **CiRCLETECH Hub** guiding document, Vision, objectives, and reporting principles for each group
- Defining research group operational principles (working principles, networking opportunities) defining review, monitoring and reporting in terms of methodology and time (frequency) and responsibilities – this is a guiding document

Skills and Competency evaluation development

Who: **Coordinator**

When: Q1 2023

What:

- Developing methodology and evaluation of predefined skills and competencies for finding skills gaps for researchers involved in the **CiRCLETECH Hub** activities
- Deploy easily to use evaluation tool makes Local group Coordinators execute evaluations for the researchers in their local group providing the basis for IDP drafting

Skills and Competency evaluation execution

Who: **Research Group Leaders**, researchers (It UNIM only)

When: Q2 2023

What:

- **Research Group Leaders** initiating the process of inviting researchers
- Researchers going through skills and competency gap evaluation to identify areas that are needs to be improved – results will be used for researchers formulating the IDP and RDP

Individual Development Plan process development (is it for UM only?)

Who: **Coordinator**, Research Group Leaders, UNIM deans

When: Q1 – Q2 2023

What:

- The coordinator initiates the process
- Developing methodology and template that supports research group leaders and researchers to draft researchers' individual development plans
- IDPs are to be approved by the Research Group Leader and the dean of the involved researcher

Individual Development Plan creation process

Who: **Research Group Leaders**, researchers (it is UNIM only)

When: Q2 – Q3 2023

What:

- **Research Group Leaders** initiating the process of inviting researchers
- Using the methodology and template created by the IDP process development, the outcome of the skills and competency evaluation, based on the interest of the researcher and their stage in the research career jointly iterating and agreed upon IDP of each researcher involved
- IDPs are to be approved by the Research Group Coordinators and the dean of the involved researcher
- Out of IDPs, each Research Group Coordinator combines theirs into a **Research Group Plan** and based on the outcomes, results and planned activities they are deciding on budget allocation available for the research group to support the realization of the RDPs

CiRCLETECH HUB Coordination processes

Who: **WP2 leader**, Research Group leaders, Coordinator

When: Q1 2023 - Continuous

What:

- Approval of the **CiRCLETECH HUB** Coordination guiding document initiates the process, reviews, meetings, documentation, and monitoring according to the **CiRCLETECH HUB** Coordination guiding document.

Research Group Coordination processes

Who: **Research Group leaders**, Local Group Coordinators, Coordinator

When: Q1 2023 - Continuous

What:

- Approval of Research Group Coordination processes guiding the document initiates the process, reviews, meetings, documentation, and monitoring according to the Research Group Coordination processes guiding the document

Local Group Coordination processes (it is only for UNIM)

Who: **Research Group Leaders**, Local group coordinator at UNIM, researchers, UNIMM deans

When: Q3 2023 - Continuous

What:

- Approval of IDPs and RDPs are initiating the process, Local Group Coordinators and UNIM deans review monitoring individual researchers' progress and activity participation evaluating it against the IDPs, creating additional supporting and correcting actions if needed
- Methodology and frequency are defined by each Local Group Coordinator and tailor-made for their group (size of the group, maturity of their researchers, etc), Local Group Coordinators inform the Coordinator about the monitoring process, annually informing deans about researchers' progress respectively

Research Expert visits

Who: **Research Group leaders**, Local Group coordinators, selected researchers

When: 2023 July

What:

- Lead researchers from all involved institutions visit each other for networking, getting familiar with available resource infrastructure, research methodologies applied, and other resources that help research group Leaders and Local Group Coordinators guide the IDP drafting process by knowing opportunities and directly contribute the delivery of D2.2 - Expert visits and research gap identification workshop.

Research gap identification workshop

Who: **Research Group leaders**, Local Group coordinators, researchers, research management team

When: 2023 July

What:

- Workshop on the following topic: identification of the level of technology currently used by the companies operating in Northern Hungary compared to state-of-the-art technology level and solutions for the same applications identified via a technology scouting. Identifying the technology gap allows the research teams to investigate social, market, financial-economic and policy-related barriers to adopt more efficient technologies, and develop solutions and actions to overcome barriers to regional development. The outcome of the workshop is supporting Deliverable D2.3 – Strategy on joint research activities (due date September 2023)

Design thinking workshops for idea generation and to promote design thinking

Who: **Research Group leaders**, Local Group coordinators, researchers, research management team

When: 2023 December 2024 June

What:

- Workshop on research proposal ideation addressing known calls using design thinking methodology, the outcome of the workshops is research proposal ideas with actions defined on proposal making focusing on mostly Horizon Europe calls, but other international funding schemes are not excluded.